

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Flexible IDF approach with endogenous inputs

Discussion paper

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Flexible IDF approach with endogenous inputs*

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Abstract

This study contributes to the theoretical development of a proxy-variable approach in modelling multiple-input, multiple-output production technology and provides empirical evidence on the link between input-use intensity and economic viability. The proxy-variable approach is used to address endogeneity of variable inputs. We focus on estimating output growth and its components attributed to quasi-fixed inputs, variable inputs, and productivity change, while treating variable inputs as endogenous.

In addition, the study contributes to the evaluation of the economic effects of selected agrochemical-saving technologies recorded in the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database (organic farming and precision agriculture technologies). The analysis provides empirical information useful for the parametrization of these technologies in terms of their production characteristics. It also examines the role of contract work as a channel through which new technologies enter the production process.

The novelty of our approach is threefold. First, it complements the existing proxy-variable literature by incorporating a flexible representation of a multiple input/output production process, ensuring consistent estimates of production technology and productivity in the presence of endogenous inputs. This presents an operational approach to identifying and estimating the parameters of a translog input distance function specified with three outputs, three variable inputs and three quasi-fixed inputs. Second, it advances the multiple-output proxy-variable approach by addressing more directly the treatment of productivity and efficiency, thereby helping to narrow the gap between the proxy-variable literature and stochastic frontier analysis. Third, it provides new empirical evidence on productivity dynamics, and the role of capacity constraints in shaping short-run production responses across European farms, with particular attention to the role of agrochemical inputs.

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1 Introduction

In February 2025, the European Commission introduced the Vision for Agriculture and Food, a comprehensive roadmap for developing a competitive, attractive, resilient, and sustainable European agri-food sector with a 2040 perspective (European Commission, 2025). A fundamental driver underpinning these ambitious goals is productivity growth. Productivity improvements can support economic prosperity for farmers and rural communities while also making farming more attractive to younger generations and contributing to environmental sustainability by enabling investment in modern technologies that reduce reliance on inputs such as fertilisers and pesticides (Mairesse et al., 2025; Mahmood et al., 2024; Polemis and Tsionas, 2022; Tey and Brindal, 2015).

Reducing chemical inputs constitutes a core objective of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Lower agrochemical dependency is closely linked to a range of environmental and societal benefits, including improved soil health, the preservation of biodiversity, and the protection of human health. By limiting the intensity of agrochemical use, agricultural systems can enhance ecosystem functioning, reduce environmental contamination, and contribute to more sustainable and resilient production systems (Parven et al., 2025; Beaumelle et al., 2023; Pandey and Pandey, 2023). At the same time, agrochemical inputs have long played a significant role in increasing crop yields and supporting food security (Jost et al., 2025; Guo et al., 2022; Tyagi et al., 2022). This duality highlights the need to balance productivity objectives with environmental and health considerations.

Designing effective agricultural policy to support productivity and sustainability requires a robust evidence base on the transformation process in agricultural production. Cechura et al. (2025) contribution is noteworthy on the effects of pesticides and fertilisers on crop production and productivity growth. The study investigates the role of agrochemical inputs as variable inputs, together with technological progress, in driving output growth and total factor productivity (TFP) growth. Drawing on a translog production function modelling and Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) data for Czech cereal farms from 2008–2020, their findings suggest that efforts to reduce reliance on agrochemicals could substantially affect farm productivity and profitability. However, as discussed in their study, the potential adverse effects of reducing agrochemical inputs may be addressed or mitigated through technological advancements. At the same time, an important question left unresolved in their analysis concerns the role of capacity constraints in shaping production possibilities and productivity. From a methodological perspective, their study also highlights the need for approaches capable of capturing the multiple-output nature of agricultural production.

In light of this, the objective of this study is to investigate the short-run, multiple-output and multiple-input production structure of EU agriculture, with particular attention to capacity constraints driven by quasi-fixed inputs. The study further analyses productivity dynamics conditional on outputs, variable inputs—namely fertilisers, pesticides, and farm capacity—with the

aim of equipping policymakers with critical insights into the drivers of productivity growth among heterogeneous European agricultural producers. In addition, it evaluates the economic effects of selected agrochemical-saving technologies recorded in the FADN database, specifically organic farming and precision agriculture technologies, with the aim of providing empirical information useful for the parameterisation of these technologies in terms of their production characteristics. It also examines the role of contract work as a channel through which new technologies are introduced into the production process.

To describe the multiple-input, multiple-output transformation process, typical of agricultural production, and investigate productivity dynamics, agricultural economists frequently estimate production functions that model the conversion of inputs into multiple outputs aggregated into total revenue. However, the characteristics of the transformation process based on the total revenue production function have important limitations. For example, they do not allow the identification of cross-output elasticities. Moreover, aggregating production into a single output, such as revenue, requires strong assumptions, and violations of these assumptions can bias estimates of both production technology and productivity (Malikov and Lien, 2021). To address this concern, the study adopts an IDF framework that accommodates multiple inputs and multiple outputs, offering a more flexible and comprehensive representation of the production process.

The choice of the IDF approach is particularly appropriate because it characterizes the production technology from the input side, is dual to the cost function and reflects the assumption that producers exert less control over outputs than over inputs. Consequently, the assumption of cost-minimizing behaviour appears especially suitable in the context of agricultural production (Kumbhakar et al., 2007). Additionally, the study employs a dynamic approach to production framework that captures the intertemporal links between production decisions by modelling of the underlying technology as a flexible IDF with quasi-fixed inputs.

Identifying the IDF, similar to identifying the production function, from observational data, presents significant econometric challenges. As noted by Marschak and Andrews (1944) real-world production does not exhibit a simple one-directional causal relationship between inputs and outputs. Instead, it is characterized by simultaneity, as producers choose inputs based on behavioural considerations and expectations. Stochastic events and conditions prevailing on farms¹—unobservable to econometricians but observable to agricultural producers—affect not only outputs but also input allocation decisions. This correlation between inputs and unobserved productivity gives rise to an endogeneity problem due to omitted variables (Latruffe et al., 2017; Zhengfei et al., 2006).

To address these challenges, Marschak and Andrews (1944) introduced the simultaneous equations framework to identify the true relationship between inputs and outputs in production models. Their work laid the foundation for a proxy-variable approaches later developed by Olley and Pakes (1996) and Levinsohn and Petrin (2003), which explicitly address endogeneity and simul-

¹Petrick and Kloss (2018) provide specific examples of these shocks and factors in their discussion of approaches to address endogeneity.

taneity in production function estimation by using structural proxies for unobserved productivity. These proxies control for time-varying productivity that is unobserved by the econometrician but anticipated by producers when making decisions. This study extends the proxy-variable approach—typically applied to single-output production functions (e.g. [Cechura et al. \(2025\)](#)), by incorporating multiple-output technology represented by the IDF in a flexible translog specification. The aim is to obtain unbiased and consistent estimates of multiple-output technology in its primal representation, together with productivity.

Although endogeneity in production estimation of production processes has received considerable academic attention, applications of proxy-variable methodologies to agricultural production with multiple outputs remain limited. By contrast, instrumental variable (IV) approaches have been used more frequently. However, identifying valid instruments—variables sufficiently correlated with an endogenous regressors but uncorrelated with the error term—is often difficult in practice ([Akerberg et al. \(2007\)](#)), which limits the feasibility of IV methods in many empirical settings.

A notable contribution to the proxy-variable literature in agriculture is the study by [Malikov and Lien \(2021\)](#), who extend the proxy-variable approach to multiple-output agricultural production using an output index function to formalize a multiple-output production model with endogenous inputs and unobserved farm productivity. Building on critiques by [Akerberg et al. \(2015a\)](#) and [Gandhi et al. \(2020\)](#), their methodology uses first-order conditions (FOC) derived from a static profit-maximization problem, combined with a Markov process for persistent productivity, to identify the multiple-output production model through a two-stage procedure for its nonparametric estimation procedure. Their framework assumes perfect competition and a common multiple-output technology across all farms, thereby excluding fully specialized producers. Compared with total-revenue production functions and multi-equation multi-product models, their approach allows the identification of the technological relationships among individual outputs along the producer’s production frontier. The present study complements [Malikov and Lien \(2021\)](#) by adopting a flexible parametric approach that imposes minimal restrictions on the technology² to estimate a multiple-output multiple-input, multiple-output transformation process. Specifically, we use a multi-output transformation function represented by a translog IDF without the separability assumption.

The novelty of this study is threefold. First, it extends the proxy-variable literature by introducing a flexible representation of multiple-input, multiple-output production within a translog input distance function (IDF) framework and develops an operational-identification estimation strategy for this setting with variable and quasi-fixed inputs, enabling consistent estimation of production technology and productivity in the presence of endogenous inputs. Second, the study advances the treatment of unobserved productivity by integrating the proxy-variable approach with concepts

²While non-parametric approaches offer certain advantages, including the absence of a need to specify a functional form, the interpretability, statistical inference capabilities, and efficiency of parametric approaches may render them more suitable for modelling agricultural production ([Florens and Simar \(2005\)](#)).

traditionally associated with stochastic frontier analysis (SFA). By first showing how efficiency can be identified, and second by explicitly separating productivity dynamics from capacity-related scale effects, the framework helps bridge the methodological gap between proxy-based production function estimation and efficiency analysis. Third, the paper provides new empirical evidence on production technology, productivity dynamics, and short-run adjustment capacity across heterogeneous European agricultural systems. Using harmonized farm-level data covering 25 EU Member States, the results show that agrochemical inputs primarily operate along an intensity margin, while quasi-fixed factors such as land, labour, and capital govern the ability of farms to adjust to input restrictions. This capacity-conditioned perspective offers new insights into the short-run production consequences of reductions in fertiliser and pesticide use, an issue of direct relevance for current EU agricultural policy debates. Existing studies with comparable EU-wide coverage remain limited (e.g., [Wimmer and Finger \(2025\)](#); [Cechura et al. \(2017\)](#)), while analyses confined to individual countries or small regional samples (e.g., [Biagini et al. \(2023\)](#); [Kellermann and Salhofer \(2014\)](#); [Mary \(2013\)](#)) provide only partial guidance for EU-level policy assessment.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the agricultural transformation process and the theoretical foundations of the IDF and its identification. Section 3 outlines the parameter estimation procedure. Section 4 describes the data. Section 5 presents the empirical results, and Section 6 provides a discussion and concluding remarks.

2 Model specification

2.1 Transformation process

Agricultural production is a complex process involving multiple inputs and multiple outputs. Producers manage this process with the aim of achieving objectives such as cost minimization or profit maximization. Under the assumption of perfectly competitive markets, producers behave as price takers and choose optimal quantities of both outputs and inputs. However, several key inputs—most notably physical capital, labour, and land—are subject to adjustment frictions, including time-to-install constraints, hiring and training costs, and production-cycle rigidities associated with planting and harvesting periods. As a result, these inputs are effectively predetermined, reflecting decisions made in earlier periods. In contrast, variable inputs such as fertilisers, pesticides, and other intermediate materials can be adjusted more flexibly. Consequently, in the short run, producers choose variable input quantities of variable inputs conditional on their predetermined inputs and their underlying productivity ([Malikov and Lien, 2021](#)).

To describe a multiple-input, multiple-output production process, production theory employs a transformation function. Consider the transformation process of an agricultural producer i ($i = 1, \dots, N$) in the time period t ($t = 1, \dots, T$), in which a non-negative vector of variable inputs $\mathbf{X}_{it} = (X_{1it}, X_{2it}, \dots, X_{Rit})$ and a non-negative vector of quasi-fixed inputs $\mathbf{Q}_{it} = (Q_{1it}, Q_{2it}, \dots, Q_{Jit})$, predetermined in time $t - 1$, are transformed into a non-negative vector of

outputs $\mathbf{Y}_{it} = (Y_{1it}, Y_{2it}, \dots, Y_{Mit})$. The corresponding transformation function with a neutral productivity component (Malikov et al., 2025) is:

$$T(\mathbf{Y}_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it} \exp\{-\omega_{it} - v_{it}\}, \mathbf{Q}_{it}) = 1 \quad (2.1)$$

where ω_{it} denotes persistent productivity, which is known and predictable to the agricultural producer, while v_{it} represents a transitory productivity shock that remains unknown to both the agricultural producer and the econometricians. Note that both ω and v are unrestricted and therefore one can use either $-\omega_{it} - v_{it}$ or $\omega_{it} + v_{it}$ in the above transformation function. Persistent productivity, which captures farm-specific characteristics such as management quality and tacit knowledge, whereas transitory shocks may arise from factors such as weather conditions, pests, unexpected equipment failures, or disruptions to labour supply (Akerberg et al., 2007). Both components are farm-specific and scale all variable inputs proportionally.

This transformation function is assumed to satisfy the standard neoclassical properties, including continuity, monotonicity (non-decreasing in inputs and non-increasing in outputs), and concavity (Chambers, 1988). It is commonly assumed that the production technology is homothetically separable in outputs. Although this assumption is not strictly required, it greatly facilitates structural identification, particularly in nonparametric settings (Malikov et al., 2025).³ In the present study, however, we employ a parametric functional form, so the separability assumption is unnecessary for either identification or estimation.

Under the behavioural assumption that producers choose variable inputs to minimize the cost of producing a given output vector, conditional on quasi-fixed inputs, and assuming that the producer operates in a perfectly competitive input markets, the production transformation process can be represented by a short-run cost function representation of the technology (Coelli et al., 2005). However, estimating a cost function requires data on variable input prices, which are often unavailable to researchers. To overcome this data limitation, this study employs a dual representation of the technology—the input distance function (IDF)—as an alternative analytical framework.⁴

2.2 Input distance function

Let multiple-input, multiple-output technology be represented by the input requirement set, which consists of all input vectors (excluding variable inputs \mathbf{Q}) capable of producing a given output vector:

$$L(\mathbf{Y}) = \{\mathbf{X} : \mathbf{X} \text{ can produce } \mathbf{Y}\} \quad (2.2)$$

³Under homothetic separability, a single-output production function can be written as $Y = f(\mathbf{X}_{it} \exp\{-\omega_{it} - v_{it}\}, \mathbf{Q}_{it})$.

⁴The duality result states that, under certain regularity conditions, there exists a one-to-one correspondence between the cost function and the IDF. Consequently, each function can be uniquely derived from the other through an appropriate mathematical transformation, as both encapsulate equivalent information about the underlying production technology (Shephard, 1953).

where $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{R+K}$ is a vector of all inputs used to produce the output vector $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}_+^M$. The input requirement set is assumed to be closed and convex for all outputs (Coelli et al., 2005), bounded by the input isoquant:

$$IsoqL(\mathbf{Y}) = \{\mathbf{X} : \mathbf{X} \in L(\mathbf{Y}), \lambda\mathbf{X} \notin L(\mathbf{Y}), \lambda < 1\} \quad (2.3)$$

and both inputs and outputs are assumed to be strongly (or freely) disposable (Kumbhakar and Lovell, 2000).

Shephard's IDF (Shephard, 1970) is then defined as a radial measure of the distance from the output vector \mathbf{Y} to Isoq $L(\mathbf{Y})$:

$$D_I(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) = \sup\{\mu > 0 : (\mathbf{Y}/\mu) \in L(\mathbf{Y})\}, \quad (2.4)$$

where μ measures the maximum degree of proportional reduction in the input vector \mathbf{X} that still allows production of a given output vector \mathbf{Y} .

By definition, the IDF describes the largest factor of proportionality μ by which the input vector \mathbf{X} can be scaled down while remaining capable of producing the output vector \mathbf{Y} with the technology available at a particular time t (Caves et al., 1982). An input-output combination is technically feasible, denoted $\mathbf{X} \in L(\mathbf{Y})$, if and only if $D(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) \geq 1$. If $D(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) = 1$, the production is not only technically feasible but also efficient (Shephard, 1970). Assuming that the input requirement set $L(\mathbf{Y})$ satisfies standard regularity conditions, the IDF possesses several useful properties, including symmetry, monotonicity, linear homogeneity of degree one in inputs, concavity in inputs, and quasi-concavity in outputs (Greene, 2005).

Incorporating the decomposition of inputs into variable and quasi-fixed components, together with a neutral productivity term, the IDF can be reformulated (including the variable inputs \mathbf{Q}) as:

$$D_I(\mathbf{Y}_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it}^*, \mathbf{Q}_{it}) = \sup\{\mu > 0 : (\mathbf{Y}_{it}/\mu) \in L(\mathbf{Y}_{it})\}, \quad (2.5)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}_{it} = (Y_{1it}, Y_{2it}, \dots, Y_{Mit})$ is a non-negative vector of outputs, $\mathbf{X}_{it}^* = \mathbf{X}_{it} \exp\{-\phi^X(\omega_{it} + v_{it})\}$, with $\mathbf{X}_{it} = (X_{1it}, X_{2it}, \dots, X_{Rit})$ is a non-negative vector of variable inputs, and $\mathbf{Q}_{it} = (Q_{1it}, Q_{2it}, \dots, Q_{Jit})$ is a non-negative vector of quasi-fixed inputs, ϕ^X is a degree of homogeneity, ω_{it} denotes persistent productivity, and v_{it} denotes a transitory productivity shock. The subscripts i and t denote the farm and time periods, respectively ($i = 1, \dots, N$, $t = 1, \dots, T$).

We impose the degree of homogeneity in variable inputs to be equal 1 (viewed as an identifying restriction) and that productivity is Hicks-neutral, then the IDF can be rewritten as:

$$D_I(\mathbf{Y}_{it}, X_{it} \exp\{\omega_{it} + v_{it}\}, \mathbf{Q}_{it}) = 1 \quad (2.6)$$

For empirical analysis, we assume that the transformation function can be well approximated by a translog (TL) IDF. Although the proxy-variable approach often employs less flexible functional

forms (e.g., the Cobb–Douglas form), these specifications can be overly restrictive and may lead to biased estimates. The advantage of the TL specification lies in its flexibility. Its second-order terms are nonzero, which allows elasticities of substitution to be observation-specific. In addition, the TL form nests the Cobb–Douglas function, making it possible to formally test the flexible specification against its restricted counterpart.

Additionally, we relax the restrictive assumption of Hicks-neutral technological change by including a time variable as a proxy for technological progress⁵ and by accounting for farm-specific effects, μ_i . The full IDF translog form of $f(\cdot)$ can be then expressed as, with $\ln D_I(\mathbf{Y}_{it}, X_{it} \exp\{\omega_{it} + v_{it}\}, \mathbf{Q}_{it}) = 0$, which is implied by 2.6:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 = & \mu_i + \sum_j \alpha_m y_{mit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \alpha_{mn} y_{mit} y_{nit} + \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} y_{mit} q_{jit} \\
& + \sum_j \beta_j q_{jit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} q_{jit} q_{lit} + \sum_r \gamma_r x_{rit}^* + \frac{1}{2} \sum_r \sum_{r'} \gamma_{rr'} x_{rit}^* x_{r'it}^* \\
& + \sum_m \sum_r \delta_{mr} y_{mit} x_{rit}^* + \sum_j \sum_r \delta'_{jr} q_{jit} x_{rit}^* + \omega_{it} + v_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

with the homogeneity conditions: $\sum_j \gamma_r = 1$, $\sum_{j'} \gamma_{rr'} = 0 \forall r$, $\sum_r \delta_{mr} = 0$, $\sum_r \delta'_{jr} = 0$; symmetry restrictions in: $\alpha_{mn} = \alpha_{nm}$, $\beta_{jl} = \beta_{lj}$ and $\gamma_{rr'} = \gamma_{r'r}$; and $x_{rit}^* = \ln(X_{it} \exp\{\omega_{it} + v_{it}\}) = x_{rit} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}$. Our IDF model treats capital (K), land (A), and labour (L) as quasi-fixed inputs, and fertiliser (F), pesticides (H)—including herbicides and other crop protection products—and other material inputs (O) as variable inputs, consistent with the empirical application. Moreover, the model specifies a vector of outputs that are predetermined, similar to quasi-fixed inputs, in period $(t-1)$.⁶ That is, y_{mit} stands for the vector of m outputs; the variables in q_{jit} are k_{it}, a_{it}, l_{it} , and the variables in x_{rit} are f_{it}, h_{it}, o_{it} .⁷

In the empirical application, equation (2.7) is normalized by other materials, which serve as the numeraire input. This results in the following specification:

⁵Since technological change has a long term character, t is included among quasi-fixed inputs. Moreover, in translog IDF model specification this allows for testing biased technological change against Hicks-neutral technological change.

⁶Specifically, we may consider farmer's decision making as a sequential process: the production mix and quasi-fixed inputs are determined based on information available at time $(t-1)$, while variable inputs are adjusted using information available at time (t) .

⁷Lowercase letters represent the logarithms of their uppercase counterparts.

$$\begin{aligned}
-o_{it}^* &= \mu_i + \sum_j \alpha_m y_{mit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \alpha_{mn} y_{mit} y_{nit} + \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} y_{mit} q_{jit} \\
&+ \sum_j \beta_j q_{jit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} q_{jit} q_{lit} + \sum_r \gamma_r \tilde{x}_{rit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_r \sum_{r'} \gamma_{rr'} \tilde{x}_{rit} \tilde{x}_{r'it} \\
&+ \sum_m \sum_r \delta_{mr} y_{mit} \tilde{x}_{rit} + \sum_j \sum_r \delta'_{jr} q_{jit} \tilde{x}_{rit}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

where $o_{it}^* = \ln(O_{it} \exp\{\omega_{it} + v_{it}\}) = o_{it} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}$;

$\tilde{x}_{r(r')it} = \ln(X_{r(r')it} \exp\{\omega_{it} + v_{it}\} / O_{it} \exp\{\omega_{it} + v_{it}\}) = x_{r(r')it} - o_{it}$, for $r, r' = f, h$. That is, we can rewrite the translog (TL) IDF as:

$$\begin{aligned}
-o_{it} &= \mu_i + \sum_j \alpha_m y_{mit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \alpha_{mn} y_{mit} y_{nit} + \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} y_{mit} q_{jit} \\
&+ \sum_j \beta_j q_{jit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} q_{jit} q_{lit} + \sum_r \gamma_r \tilde{x}_{rit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_r \sum_{r'} \gamma_{rr'} \tilde{x}_{rit} \tilde{x}_{r'it} \\
&+ \sum_m \sum_r \delta_{mr} y_{mit} \tilde{x}_{rit} + \sum_j \sum_r \delta'_{jr} q_{jit} \tilde{x}_{rit} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

The TL IDF function in (2.9) can be decomposed into two parts: one involving quasi-fixed outputs and input variables predetermined at time $t - 1$, and another involving variable inputs. Thus, the TL IDF in (2.9) can be written as $T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) + TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2)$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) &= \sum_r \gamma_r \tilde{x}_{rit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_r \sum_{r'} \gamma_{rr'} \tilde{x}_{rit} \tilde{x}_{r'it} + \sum_m \sum_r \delta_{mr} y_{mit} \tilde{x}_{rit} \\
&+ \sum_j \sum_r \delta'_{jr} q_{jit} \tilde{x}_{rit}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

is a translog function with variable inputs F, H, O ; and

$$\begin{aligned}
TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2) &= \mu_i + \sum_j \alpha_m y_{mit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \alpha_{mn} y_{mit} y_{nit} + \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} y_{mit} q_{jit} \\
&+ \sum_j \beta_j q_{jit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} q_{jit} q_{lit} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

is a translog function with quasi-fixed outputs, inputs (K, A, L) and t . We denote $\beta_1 = (\gamma_r, \gamma_{rr'}, \delta_{mr}, \delta'_{jr})$ and $\beta_2 = (\mu_i, \alpha_m, \alpha_{mn}, \alpha'_{mj}, \beta_j, \beta_{jl})$ for $r, r' = f, h$; $j, l = k, a, l, t$ and m, n are M outputs.

2.3 Identification

In this subsection, we demonstrate that all the parameters in the TL IDF in (2.7) or (2.9) can be identified using a multi-step procedure. Structural identification of the model is facilitated by several assumptions concerning the agricultural transformation process, the broader economic environment, and the behaviour and decision-making patterns of agricultural producers.

Assumption 1. Perfectly competitive markets – Agricultural producers are assumed to operate in perfectly competitive output and variable input markets. Under this assumption, agricultural producers behave as price takers, implying that they cannot influence market prices.

Assumption 2. Cost-minimising behaviour – Agricultural producers face output uncertainty due to factors beyond their control, while maintaining complete control over their input decisions. Given this constraint, the producer’s objective is to minimize expected short-run production costs for a target level of outputs.

Assumption 3. Dynamic decision process – The decision process in crop production is sequential and is divided into two stages: i) planning season ($t - 1$) and ii) growing and harvesting season (t). During the planning season, producers determine levels of quasi-fixed inputs—capital, land, and labour. Subsequently, during the growing and harvesting season, they choose levels of material inputs, including fertiliser, pesticides, and other intermediate inputs, to achieve their production objectives. Under this timing structure, inputs fall into two distinct categories. Capital, land, and labour function as state variables that are quasi-fixed once determined in the planning stage based on past productivity and are therefore unresponsive to contemporaneous productivity shocks in period t . In contrast, material inputs are flexible and can be adjusted in response to current productivity.

Assumption 4. Transformation function assumption – The production technology takes the form specified in (2.1) and is well represented by a TL IDF with Hicks-neutral productivity. The TL IDF is assumed to be twice differentiable, homogeneous of degree one in inputs, non-decreasing and concave in inputs, and non-increasing and quasi-concave in outputs. This framework allows derivation of the standard properties of production technology, including measures of technical efficiency.

Assumption 5. Productivity process – Persistent productivity is known to the agricultural producer at the time of decision-making (period t) and evolves according to a first-order Markov process. The transitory productivity shock is assumed to have zero mean and to be uncorrelated with all variables in the IDF.

The validity of these identifying assumptions is assessed using specification tests proposed by Levinsohn and Petrin (2003). The first test examines whether the estimates remain stable when inputs are classified differently into quasi-fixed and variable groups. The second test evaluates the correlation between all inputs in periods t and $(t - 1)$ and the innovation in productivity in period t .

Under our assumptions, the optimization problem can be written as:

$$\text{Minimize } W'_{X_{it}} X_{it} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad T(Y_{it}, X_{it} e^{\omega_{it} + v_{it}}, Q_{it}) = 1 \quad (2.12)$$

The Lagrangian for cost minimization using the transformation function is:

$$L = W'_{X_{it}} X_{it} + \lambda [T(Y_{it}, X_{it} e^{\omega_{it} + v_{it}}, Q_{it}) - 1], \quad (2.13)$$

and the corresponding first-order conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} W_{X_{jit}} + \lambda \frac{\partial T(\cdot)}{\partial X_{jit}} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow W_{X_{jit}} + \lambda \frac{\partial \ln T(\cdot)}{\partial \ln X_{jit}} \frac{T(\cdot)}{X_{jit}} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit} + \lambda \varepsilon_{X_{jit}} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \sum_j W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit} + \lambda \sum_j \varepsilon_{X_{jit}} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

where $\varepsilon_{X_{jit}} = \frac{\partial \ln T(\cdot)}{\partial \ln X_{jit}^*}$ for $\ln X_{jit}^* = \ln X_{jit} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}$.

If $T(\cdot)$ is homogeneous of degree 1 in X_j^* , then $\sum_j \varepsilon_{jit} = 1$, then we can write: $C_{it} + \lambda = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda = -C$. That is, we can write $W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit} + \lambda \varepsilon_{X_{jit}} = 0$ as:

$$s_{X_{jit}} = \varepsilon_{X_{jit}}, \quad (2.14)$$

where $s_{X_{jit}} = \frac{W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit}}{C_{it}}$ with $C_{it} = \sum_j W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit}$ is cost share of respective variable input.

Using the TL function in (2.8), gives:

$$\varepsilon_{X_{rit}} = \gamma_r + \sum_{r'} \gamma_{rr'} \tilde{x}_{r'it} + \sum_m \delta_{mr} y_{mit} + \sum_j \delta'_{jr} q_{jit}, \quad X \in (F, H) \quad \text{and} \quad r = f, h. \quad (2.15)$$

The share equations for fertilisers and pesticides variable inputs are $s_{Fit} \equiv \frac{W_{Fit} F_{it}}{\sum_j W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit}}$ and $s_{Hit} \equiv \frac{W_{Hit} H_{it}}{\sum_j W_{X_{jit}} X_{jit}}$ and the corresponding input elasticities of F and H from the translog function in (2.7) are

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{Fit} &= \alpha_1 + \alpha_{11} \tilde{f}_{it} + \alpha_{12} \tilde{h}_{it} + \delta_{11} y_{1it} + \delta_{12} y_{12it} + \delta_{13} y_{3it} + \delta'_{11} k_{it} + \delta'_{12} a_{it} + \delta'_{13} l_{it} + \delta'_{14} t_{it} \\ \varepsilon_{Hit} &= \alpha_2 + \alpha_{21} \tilde{f}_{it} + \alpha_{22} \tilde{h}_{it} + \delta_{21} y_{1it} + \delta_{22} y_{12it} + \delta_{23} y_{3it} + \delta'_{21} k_{it} + \delta'_{22} a_{it} + \delta'_{23} l_{it} + \delta'_{24} t_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

Note that ε_{Fit} and ε_{Hit} include all the parameters in β_1 .

2.3.1 Step 1

The first step identifies the β_1 parameters. To achieve this, we take logarithm of equation (2.14), add stochastic terms v_{Fit} and v_{Hit} and express them for F and H as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\ln s_{Fit} &= \ln \varepsilon_{Fit} - v_{Fit} \\ \ln s_{Hit} &= \ln \varepsilon_{Hit} - v_{Hit}\end{aligned}\tag{2.17}$$

where s_{Fit} and s_{Hit} are defined in (2.16). Note that persistent productivity ω does not appear in (2.17), therefore these equations do not have endogeneity, even though $f = \ln(F)$ and $h = \ln(H)$ appear in the equations through ε_{Fit} and ε_{Hit} . Endogeneity occurs only when f, h and ω appear together in the same equation. Therefore, (2.17) can be estimated using non-linear least squares (NLS) by minimizing residual sum of squares:

$$S = \sum_r [\ln s_{rit} - \ln \varepsilon_{rit}]^2, r = F, H\tag{2.18}$$

to obtain consistent estimates of the parameters in ε_{Mit} and ε_{Hit} . This step therefore identifies the component $T(\cdot; \beta_1)$.

2.3.2 Step 2

In this step, we identify the remaining parameters in β_2 . To do so, first we express ω_{it} in expressed as a function of observable data and the estimated parameters from Step 1 (β_1) using the FOC. We then assume that ω follows a Markov process. Using these two elements, the input distance function is rewritten in terms of β_2 and the dynamics of the ω function. The details are follows.

(i) The FOC with respect to F implies:

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{Fit} \exp(\omega_{it}) &= \frac{w_{Fit} F_{it}}{C(\cdot)} \\ \Rightarrow \omega_{it} &= \ln(w_{Fit} F_{it}) - \ln(\varepsilon_{Fit}) - \ln C(\cdot) \\ &= \ln(w_{Fit} F_{it}) - \ln(\varepsilon_{Fit}) - \ln \frac{w^T x}{D_I(\cdot)} \\ &= \ln \frac{w_{Fit} F_{it}}{w^T x} - \ln(\varepsilon_{Fit}) + T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) + TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2)\end{aligned}$$

which can be written as

$$\omega_{it} = RF(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) + TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2).\tag{2.19}$$

Similarly, the FOC for H gives

$$\omega_{it} = RH(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) + TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2)\tag{2.20}$$

where $RF(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) \equiv \ln\left(\frac{w_{Fit}F_{it}}{w^T x}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{Fit}) + T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ and $RH(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) \equiv \ln\left(\frac{w_{Hit}H_{it}}{w^T x}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{Hit}) + T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ which are known since they depend on estimated parameters from Step 1. So $RF(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ and $RH(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ can be treated as estimated variables, and we denote them as RF_{it} and RH_{it} .⁸

- (ii) We follow the proxy variable literature (e.g. [Olley and Pakes \(1996\)](#), [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#), [Akerberg et al. \(2015b\)](#), [Gandhi et al. \(2020\)](#)) and assume that persistent productivity ω_{it} follows a Markov process. The most commonly used form is the first order (AR(1)) Markov process, i.e., $\omega_{it} = \mathbb{E}(\omega_{it}|\omega_{it-1}, x_{rit}) + \eta_{it} = \rho\omega_{it-1} + \eta_{it}$ where η_{it} a transient productivity shock (productivity innovation) with zero mean and is uncorrelated with all variables in the production function.⁹

Using [\(2.19\)](#)

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{it} &= \rho\omega_{it-1} + \eta_{it} = \rho[RF_{it-1} - TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2)] + \eta_{it} \\ &= \rho RF_{it-1} - \rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it}.\end{aligned}\tag{2.21}$$

Similarly, using [\(2.20\)](#):

$$\omega_{it} = \rho RH_{it-1} - \rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it}.\tag{2.22}$$

We take the average of these two expressions to obtain a single measure of ω_{it} which is:

$$\omega_{it} = \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} - \rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it},\tag{2.23}$$

where $\bar{R}_{it-1} = [RF_{it-1} + RH_{it-1}]/2$. Finally, we rewrite the translog function as

$$\begin{aligned}-o_{it}^* - T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) &= TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2) + \rho[\bar{R}_{it-1} - TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2)] + v_{it} + \eta_{it} \\ \Rightarrow \tilde{o}_{it} &= TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} - \rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) + e_{it}\end{aligned}\tag{2.24}$$

where $\tilde{o}_{it} \equiv -o_{it}^* - T(y_{mit}, \tilde{x}_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ and $e_{it} = v_{it} + \eta_{it}$. One can then use NLS to [\(2.24\)](#) to estimate ρ and β_2 parameters. Note that ρ is the coefficient of \bar{R}_{it-1} which identifies ρ and $\rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) = TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \rho \beta_2)$ identifies β_2 . So Steps 1 and 2 together identify both β_1 and β_2 which are the parameters of the input distance function in [\(2.7\)](#), except for the farm effects μ_i . Productivity ω_{it} can then be obtained by averaging ω_{it} from

⁸Note that there are two equations for ω_{it} , because there is a single ω but two normalized variable inputs. This means that ω can be obtained from either equation or by taking an average of the two.

⁹Having determinants of ω helps identification because it provides independent variation other than the inputs. However, the model remains identified even without determinant variables such as subsidy, R&D, FDI, or similar factors.

(2.19) and (2.20).

Remark 1 Note that $TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2)$ has μ_i which are likely to be correlated with y_{mit} , q_{jit} , y_{mit-1} , q_{jit-1} and possibly with other variables in the $TL(\cdot)$ function. So we need to address this issue before using NLS in (2.24).

Remark 2 Equation (2.24) is specified under the assumption that all farms are technically efficient, i.e. $(D_I(y, x) = 1 \Rightarrow_I (y, x) = u_{it} = 0)$. If we relax this assumption, we may introduce the inefficiency term in (2.24) as $e_{it} = u_{it} + v_{it} + \eta_{it}$ with $u_{it} = \zeta_i + \psi_{it}$, where ζ_i stands for persistent inefficiency and ψ_{it} is transient inefficiency that are distributed: We may identify them following multistep procedure introduced by Bokusheva and Cechura (2017) or Bokusheva et al. (2022) for the case with determinants of inefficiency with the exception that we do not distinguish between transient inefficiency, ψ_{it} , and transient productivity shocks, η_{it} .¹⁰

Rewrite $TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2) - \rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2)$ fully to bring μ_i to light. Using (2.11) and taking a lag of it, yields $TL(y_{mit}, q_{jit}; \beta_2) - \rho TL(y_{mit-1}, q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) = \mu_i(1 - \rho) + \sum_m \alpha_m (y_{mit} - \rho y_{mit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \beta_{mn} [y_{mit} y_{nit} - \rho y_{mit-1} y_{nit-1}] + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} [y_{mit} q_{jit} - \rho y_{mit-1} q_{jit-1}] + \sum_j \beta_j (q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}]$. Then we use it in (2.24), to get:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{o}_{it} = & \mu_i(1 - \rho) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} + \sum_m \alpha_m (y_{mit} - \rho y_{mit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \beta_{mn} [y_{mit} y_{nit} - \rho y_{mit-1} y_{nit-1}] + \\ & + \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} [y_{mit} q_{jit} - \rho y_{mit-1} q_{jit-1}] + \sum_j \beta_j (q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}] + e_{it}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

First differencing (FD) (2.25) will get rid of μ_i and the resulting equation can be estimated using NLS. Note that ρ is identified from the coefficient of \bar{R}_{it-1} and the β_2 coefficients are identified from the first difference of $\sum_m \alpha_m (y_{mit} - \rho y_{mit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \beta_{mn} [y_{mit} y_{nit} - \rho y_{mit-1} y_{nit-1}] + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} [y_{mit} q_{jit} - \rho y_{mit-1} q_{jit-1}] + \sum_j \beta_j (q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}]$.

However, the problem of using FD in the presence of lagged variables leads to a loss of two observations for each i (a total of $2N$ observations) because of the presence of two lagged terms. An alternative approach is to use correlated random effects, e.g., $\mu_i = z'_i \gamma_i + \xi_i$ where z_i are time-invariant variables that are correlated with those appearing in (2.25), i.e., y_{mit} , q_{jit} , y_{mit-1} , q_{jit-1} , $\forall m$ and $\forall j$. In the absence of suitable z_i variables, one can use Mundlak's (1978) formulation based on farm-specific means (by farm) y_m , q_j , i.e. \bar{y}_m , \bar{q}_j . That is,

$$\mu_i = \sum_m \gamma'_m \bar{y}_m + \sum_j \gamma''_j \bar{q}_j + \chi_i, \quad \forall m \text{ and } \forall j \quad (2.26)$$

¹⁰In fact, changes in transient inefficiency can be regarded as another source of transient productivity shocks in the framework with inefficient farms. In this study, technical efficiency is not estimated and remains an unidentified component of productivity growth.

where χ_i is uncorrelated with the right-hand-side variables in (2.25). Having identified β_1 and β_2 , we can estimate ω_{it} averaging ω_{it} from (2.19) and (2.20).

3 Estimation

To avoid repetition, this section briefly outlines the parameter estimation process. The estimation is conducted in three steps, using NLS and the nonlinear mixed-effects model estimator (NLME).

3.1 Step 1

In this step, we use the FOC with respect to material inputs to estimate the parameters in $T(\cdot)$, i.e., β_1 . The relevant equations are (2.17), $\ln s_{Xit} = \ln(\varepsilon_{Xit}) - v_{it}$, $X \in F, H, O$. We estimate (2.17) using nonlinear least squares [Bates and Watts \(1988\)](#), [Bates and Chambers \(1992\)](#), and [Moré \(1978\)](#) by minimizing residual sum of squares in (2.18).

3.2 Step 2

In this step, we estimate the parameters in β_2 . The estimating equation is (2.25) which is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\omega}_{it} = & \mu_i(1 - \rho) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} + \sum_m \alpha_m (y_{mit} - \rho y_{mit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \beta_{mn} [y_{mit} y_{nit} - \rho y_{mit-1} y_{nit-1}] + \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} [y_{mit} q_{jit} - \rho y_{mit-1} q_{jit-1}] + \sum_j \beta_j (q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}] + e_{it}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

where $e_{it} = v_{it} + \eta_{it}$ and η_{it} is an *i.i.d.* productivity innovation that is not correlated with X_{it} , $X \in F, H, O$, and any other variables in the model. Using (2.26) in (3.1) and estimating γ_j along with the other parameters in (3.1) the model to be estimated in the empirical part is:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\omega}_{it} = & \left(\sum_m \gamma'_m \bar{y}_{mi} + \sum_j \gamma''_j \bar{q}_{ji} + \chi_i \right) (1 - \rho) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} + \sum_m \alpha_m (y_{mit} - \rho y_{mit-1}) + \quad (3.2) \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_n \beta_{mn} [y_{mit} y_{nit} - \rho y_{mit-1} y_{nit-1}] + \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \sum_j \alpha'_{mj} [y_{mit} q_{jit} - \rho y_{mit-1} q_{jit-1}] + \sum_j \beta_j (q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}] + e_{it}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

And, because of the presence of the χ_i term, we use NLME [\[1\]](#) to estimate (3.2).

¹¹NLME is a generalization of linear mixed-effects model, where the conditional mean of the outcome, given the random effects, is a non-linear function of both the coefficients and the random effects [StataCorp \(2023\)](#)

3.3 Step 3

Productivity, ω_{it} , is estimated by averaging ω_{it} from (2.19) and (2.20). After estimating ω_{it} , we can estimate the productivity change component $\dot{\omega}_{it}$:

$$\dot{\omega}_{it} = \omega_{it} - \omega_{it-1} \quad (3.4)$$

4 Data

The study employs panel data drawn from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database provided by the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI). The FADN offers harmonized microeconomic (physical as well as financial) data on roughly 80,000 farms throughout the European Union (EU). The analysis is based on data from 25 European countries¹² covering the period 2008–2021. Specifically, this study investigates farms specializing in field crop production, corresponding to the following FADN types of farming: TF14-15 Specialist cereals, oilseeds and protein crops; TF14-16 Specialist other field crops; TF14-60 Mixed crops; and TF14-80 Mixed crops and livestock.

Furthermore, data from the Czech Republic and Germany are employed to parametrize the impact of organic farming. These two countries are selected due to the substantial share of organic farming in the Czech Republic and the high level of organic food consumption in Germany.

The IDF models distinguish three variable inputs—fertilisers, pesticides, and other materials; three quasi-fixed inputs—land, capital, and labour; and three outputs. Fertilisers (F , code SE295 in FADN) refer to the costs of purchasing fertilisers and soil improvers. Pesticides (P , code SE300 in FADN) refer to the costs of purchasing plant protection products, traps, and baits, bird scarers, anti-hail shells, frost protection, etc. (excluding those used for forests). Other materials (O) are calculated as the sum of total specific costs (SE281) and total agricultural overhead (SE336), excluding fertilisers (SE295) and pesticides (SE300). Land (L) is expressed in hectares of farm Utilised Agricultural Area (SE025). Capital (K , SE465) is measured as the total fixed assets and labour (W , SE010) is measured in Annual Work Unit (AWU). Output variables represent the value of cereal production (SE140) (C); other crop output (measured as the difference between the value of total crop production (SE135) and the value of cereal production) and livestock output (calculated as the sum of cows’ milk and milk products (SE216) and other livestock output (SE206 - SE216)) (AOC), and other output (SE256) (AOO)).

Monetary variables are deflated using the price indices for the respective EU country from the EUROSTAT database (2010 = 100). The capital input is adjusted for inflation by using the index of purchase prices for agricultural production inputs, specifically for materials. The price index for fertilisers and soil improvers is used to adjust the fertiliser input, the price index for plant protection products and pesticides is used to adjust the pesticide input, and the price index of goods

¹²The Appendix (Table A1) provides a detailed list of the countries.

and services currently consumed in agriculture is used to deflate the other input materials. The output variables are deflated using the producer price indices for agricultural products (outputs), namely, the price index for the cereals (for SE140), the price index for the crops (for SE135-SE140), the price index of milk and milk products (for SE216), the price index for animal production (for SE206-SE216) and the price index for the production of agricultural inputs (for SE256).

For the analysis of the effect of organic farming, as well as the role of contracted work, an alternative specification of capital is used (see Table [1](#)). In addition, a second specification is considered in which contracted work is included in other materials, while capital is represented only by depreciation.

As organic farming in the Czech Republic is predominantly represented in cattle and sheep production (TF14-49 and TF14-48) and in Germany in milk production (TF14-45 and TF14-70 Mixed livestock), the study additionally provides estimates of the flexible IDF for these two production specializations. These models again distinguish three variable inputs: feed (SE310) (FD), other specific livestock costs (SM), and other materials (O); three quasi-fixed inputs: land (SE025), capital, and labour (SE010); and three outputs. Other specific livestock costs are calculated as the difference between total specific livestock costs ($SE309 \times SE080$) and feed for grazing livestock (SE310). Other materials are calculated as the sum of total specific costs (SE281) and total agricultural overheads (SE336), excluding contracted work (SE350) and specific livestock costs. Capital is measured as the sum of contracted work (SE350) and depreciation (SE360). To assess the role of contracted work within this model, an alternative formulation is also estimated in which contracted work is included in other materials.

In the case of milk production, the output variables represent the value of cow and sheep milk production ($SE216 + SE245$) (MLK), other crop and livestock output (AOC) (measured as the sum of the value of total crop production (SE135) and the difference between the value of total livestock production (SE206) and the value of milk production ($SE216 + SE245$)), and other output (SE256) (AOO). In the case of meat production, the outputs are defined as beef and sheep meat production ($SE220 + SE230$) (M), other crop and livestock output (measured as $SE135 + SE206 - SE220 - SE230$) (AOC), and other output (SE256) (AOO). Descriptions of the variables and the deflators used are provided in Table [1](#).

In addition, a model of precision agriculture is also specified. For its estimation, data from the Czech Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN-CZ), provided by the Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information, are used. The FADN-CZ database collects information on the use of precision agriculture technologies, classified into the following categories: A) technologies in crop production, namely: (i) soil cultivation systems (based on digital soil mapping); (ii) seeding systems; (iii) fertilisation systems (e.g. variable-rate fertiliser application, remote sensing); (iv) crop protection systems (e.g. variable-rate application of plant protection products, pesticide-spraying robots and drones); (v) autonomous machine guidance; (vi) the use of robots in vegetable, fruit, and wine production; and (vii) other technologies in crop production; B) technologies in live-

Table 1: Description of IDF variables - organic and precision farming

Cereals production		
Variable	Description (FADN code)	Price indices (2010=100)
Cereals	Cereals production (SE140)	Cereals
Other crop and livestock output	Other crop output (SE135-SE140) and livestock output (milk (SE216) and other livestock output (SE206 - SE216)	Crop, Milk, Animal
Other farm output	Other farm output (SE256)	Agricultural goods
Fertilisers	Purchased fertilisers and soil improvers (SE295)	Fertilisers
Pesticides	Plant protection products, traps, etc.(SE300)	Plant protection products
Other materials	Total specific costs and total farming overheads (SE281+SE336) excluding specific livestock costs	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Land	Utilised agricultural area (SE025)	
Labour	Total labour input in annual working unit (AWU, SE010)	
Capital	Depreciation of fixed assets and contracted work (SE360 + SE350)	Goods and services contributing to agricultural investment
Milk production		
Variable	Description (FADN code)	Price indices (2010=100)
Milk	Cow and sheep milk production (SE216 + SE245)	Milk
Other crop and livestock output	Total crop and livestock output except milk (SE135-SE216-SE245)	Agricultural goods
Other farm output	Other farm output (SE256)	Agricultural goods
Feed	Feed for grazing livestock (SE310)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Other specific livestock costs	Difference between total specific livestock costs (SE309 × SE080) and feed for grazing livestock (SE310)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Other materials	Total specific costs and total farming overheads (SE281+SE336), excluding fertilisers (SE295) and pesticides (SE300)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Land	Utilised agricultural area (SE025)	
Labour	Total labour input in annual working unit (AWU, SE010)	
Capital	Depreciation of fixed assets and contracted work (SE360 + SE350)	Goods and services contributing to agricultural investment
Meat production		
Variable	Description (FADN code)	Price indices (2010=100)
Meat	Beef and sheep meat production (SE220 + SE230)	Agricultural goods
Other crop and livestock output	Total crop and livestock output except beef and sheep meat (SE135-SE220-SE230)	Agricultural goods
Other farm output	Other farm output (SE256)	Agricultural goods
Feed	Feed for grazing livestock (SE310)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Other specific livestock costs	Difference between total specific livestock costs (SE309 × SE080) and feed for grazing livestock (SE310)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Other materials	Total specific costs and total farming overheads (SE281+SE336) excluding specific livestock costs	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Land	Utilised agricultural area (SE025)	
Labour	Total labour input in annual working unit (AWU, SE010)	
Capital	Depreciation of fixed assets and contracted work (SE360 + SE350)	Goods and services contributing to agricultural investment
Precision agriculture		
Variable	Description (FADN code)	Price indices (2010=100)
Cereals	Cereals output (SE140)	Cereals (SE140)
Other crop and livestock output	Total output except cereals and other farm output (SE131-SE140-SE256)	Agricultural goods
Other farm output	Other farm output (SE256)	Agricultural goods
Specific materials	Total specific crop costs (SE284 × SE025)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Other materials	Total specific costs excluding specific crop costs (SE281-SE284 × SE025)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Overheads	Total farming overheads (SE336)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Land	Utilised agricultural area (SE025)	
Labour	Total labour input in annual working unit (AWU, SE010)	
Capital	Depreciation of fixed assets (SE360)	Goods and services contributing to agricultural investment

stock production, namely: (i) automated animal systems (e.g. health-monitoring sensors, activity-monitoring systems, feeding-management systems); (ii) automatic milking systems; (iii) stable and farm management systems (e.g. environmental sensors, video-surveillance systems, sound-monitoring systems); (iv) technologies in pig and poultry production (e.g. automated microclimate control, animal-growth monitoring, damaged-egg detection systems); and (v) other technologies in livestock production.

The sample used in this study is based on national surveys conducted in the period 2017–2021 and consists of 545 agricultural holdings. More precisely, the sample contains 1,956 observations, including 446 specialist cereals, oilseeds and protein crops farms (76% of observations) and 179 general field crop farms (24% of observations), according to the FADN farm typology. The variables used in the model for precision agriculture are described in Table 1.

Since not all farms in the database have complete information, observations for farms with negative or zero values of cereal/milk/meat production, land, labour, capital, or material inputs are excluded from the dataset. Furthermore, holdings with fewer than three consecutive years of observations are excluded from the sample. This procedure reduces problems associated with the entry and exit of agricultural holdings from the database. The final sample sizes are presented in Table A1 and A10 in the Appendix, together with summary statistics.

5 Results

5.1 Results for European countries

5.1.1 Production technology and capacity

This section analyses the short-run production structure of EU agriculture, with particular attention to capacity constraints driven by quasi-fixed inputs. By estimating a multi-output input distance function (IDF) that distinguishes between variable inputs and quasi-fixed factors (representing capacity), we develop a capacity-conditioned framework for agricultural production. This approach enables a consistent interpretation of elasticities and short-run scale properties across EU member states, while also facilitating systematic comparison of their capacity characteristics.

We start by presenting a summary of the parameter estimates for the short-run multiple-output and multiple-input production technology characterized by the IDF, focusing primarily on its first-order properties. Production elasticities are evaluated at the sample means,¹³ making them directly comparable across EU member states under the common model specification and normalization. Within a short-run production framework, the technology is evaluated conditional on quasi-fixed inputs (land, labour, and capital). The complete set of parameter estimates is presented in the appendix in tables from [A2](#) to [A9](#).

Table [2](#) presents output elasticities for cereals, other crop output, and other farm output, along with elasticities for variable and quasi-fixed inputs. These elasticities vary across product categories, highlighting the heterogeneity in production structures across EU member states. In most cases, cereal production shows the strongest marginal responsiveness, while the aggregate ‘other production’ category exhibits the weakest, consistent with its broader and more heterogeneous composition. Importantly, the theoretical assumptions—monotonicity of outputs and inputs, as well as quasi-concavity of variable inputs¹⁴ are satisfied in all cases. Overall, first-order parameters are highly significant, and this significance generally extends to most second-order parameters and the productivity term.

¹³Since outputs and inputs are normalized by their geometric mean, the estimated first-order parameters reflect output/input elasticities at the sample mean.

¹⁴The monotonicity requirements for outputs and inputs require $\alpha_r < 0$ for $r = C, AOC, AOO$ and $\beta_j > 0$ for $j = f, p, o$, respectively. Diminishing marginal returns (concavity) in variable inputs require $\beta_{jj} + \beta_j^2 - \beta_j < 0$ for $j = f, p, o$. Note that we restrict attention to the first principal minors of the Hessian (the matrix of second derivatives of the production function) since convex technologies (which imply diminishing returns to scale) are not required; only diminishing returns to scale are imposed.

Table 2: Short-run output and input elasticities by EU member states

EU member state	Output Elasticities			SRTS	Variable Input Elasticities			Quasi-Fixed Input Elasticities		
	y_C	y_{AOC}	y_{AOO}		x_F	x_P	x_O	x_L	x_W	x_K
Austria	-0.053***	-0.074***	-0.112***	4.184	0.094***	0.059***	0.847	-0.419***	-0.091***	-0.054***
Belgium	-0.068***	-0.15***	-0.135***	2.833	0.114***	0.123***	0.763	-0.49***	-0.165***	-0.036***
Bulgaria	-0.117***	-0.098***	-0.005***	4.545	0.215***	0.101***	0.684	-0.466***	-0.06***	-0.042***
Czechia	-0.106***	-0.125***	-0.057***	3.472	0.12***	0.11***	0.77	-0.285***	-0.148***	-0.077***
Denmark	-0.056***	-0.061***	-0.129***	4.065	0.116***	0.076***	0.808	-0.381***	-0.227***	-0.075***
Estonia	-0.221***	-0.103***	-0.053***	2.653	0.169***	0.05***	0.781	-0.313***	-0.071***	-0.045**
Finland	-0.076***	-0.031***	-0.078***	5.405	0.118***	0.052***	0.83	-0.294***	-0.153***	-0.138***
France	-0.108***	-0.058***	-0.056***	4.505	0.185***	0.135***	0.68	-0.44***	-0.059***	-0.05***
Germany	-0.144***	-0.123***	-0.134***	2.494	0.131***	0.099***	0.77	-0.314***	-0.103***	-0.016***
Greece	-0.135***	-0.12***	-0.003*	3.876	0.172***	0.08***	0.748	-0.369***	-0.168***	-0.058***
Hungary	-0.178***	-0.072***	-0.03***	3.571	0.15***	0.096***	0.754	-0.434***	-0.124***	-0.021***
Ireland	-0.148***	-0.067***	-0.052***	3.745	0.201***	0.105***	0.694	-0.447***	-0.056	-0.024
Italy	-0.249***	-0.176***	-0.013***	2.283	0.157***	0.069***	0.774	-0.259***	-0.081***	-0.023***
Latvia	-0.226***	-0.093***	-0.052***	2.695	0.168***	0.064***	0.768	-0.333***	-0.105***	-0.067***
Lithuania	-0.199***	-0.133***	-0.022***	2.825	0.226***	0.088***	0.686	-0.364***	-0.079***	-0.047***
Luxemburg	-0.219***	-0.102***	-0.188***	1.965	0.132***	0.083***	0.785	-0.247*	-0.055	-0.15**
Netherlands	-0.002	-0.172***	-0.087***	3.831	0.073***	0.135***	0.792	-0.464***	-0.062***	-0.072***
Poland	-0.134***	-0.073***	-0.063***	3.704	0.149***	0.08***	0.771	-0.388***	-0.101***	-0.082***
Portugal	-0.255***	-0.094***	-0.033***	2.618	0.101***	0.086***	0.813	-0.14***	-0.15***	-0.059***
Romania	-0.14***	-0.088***	-0.021***	4.016	0.175***	0.097***	0.728	-0.548***	-0.089***	-0.029***
Slovakia	-0.142***	-0.09***	-0.045***	3.61	0.13***	0.098***	0.772	-0.301***	-0.106***	-0.029***
Slovenia	-0.135***	-0.077***	-0.121***	3.003	0.071***	0.041***	0.888	-0.274***	-0.006	-0.012
Spain	-0.313***	-0.101***	-0.013***	2.342	0.208***	0.065***	0.727	-0.247***	-0.053***	-0.074***
Sweden	-0.133***	-0.12***	-0.088***	2.933	0.141***	0.048***	0.811	-0.228***	-0.132***	-0.007
United Kingdom	-0.179***	-0.118***	-0.07***	2.725	0.154***	0.121***	0.725	-0.278***	-0.131***	-0.077***

Variable input elasticities are uniformly modest across EU member states, with fertilisers typically ranging between 0.1 and 0.2, and pesticides even lower, around 0.05 to 0.1. Since the IDF is homogeneous of degree one in variable inputs, these estimates suggest that most of the short-run adjustment required for output expansion is absorbed by the residual category of other material inputs used for normalization. Figure 1 shows that in EU member states, the responsiveness of variable inputs is largely driven by other material inputs, while fertilisers and pesticides play only a minor role. This pattern indicates that fertilisers and pesticides operate primarily along the intensity margin—that is, they support production within existing technological and structural conditions rather than driving proportional output expansion.

With respect to the elasticities of quasi-fixed inputs, Table 1 shows that they are negative for all member states. This result supports the interpretation of quasi-fixed inputs as capacity shifters that decrease the variable inputs required to produce a given output vector. Thus, land, labour, and capital play a central role in determining short-run production possibilities in EU agriculture. Differences in the magnitude of these elasticities across member states highlight substantial heterogeneity in structural conditions and factor endowments. The only consistent pattern is the dominant role of the land as a capacity shifter. In contrast, the effects of labour and capital are country-specific and considerably smaller than those of land in all member states.

Figure 1: Composition of variable input elasticities across EU member states

Figure 2: Capacity versus chemical input elasticities in EU agriculture

Figure 2 compares the elasticities of fertiliser and pesticide with the aggregate capacity elasticity, i.e. the sum of quasi-fixed input elasticities. We observe a clear and robust pattern across EU member states. In particular, the capacity effects considerably dominate chemical input elasticities. While fertilisers and pesticides contribute positively to marginal production, their low elasticities imply that chemical inputs play only a limited role in accommodating proportional output expansion in the short run.

As a result, the short-run returns to scale shown in Table 1 should not be interpreted as evidence of overall increasing returns. Instead, they reflect the scaling of variable inputs within the constraints imposed by fixed capacity. Seeing that fertilisers and pesticides have low elasticities, proportional increases in output require only modest increases in these chemical inputs, while land, labour, and capital remain fixed at time t . Consequently, the negative sum of the output elasticities is small, leading to relatively high short-term returns to scale. Notably, countries with higher short-run returns to scale do not consistently exhibit higher fertiliser or pesticide elasticities, reinforcing the interpretation that these scale properties are driven by fixed capacity rather than chemical inputs.

In summary, the results on production technology and capacity indicate that the estimated short-run technology reveals a clear distinction between the scale and intensity margins. Output expansion is predominantly constrained by capacity and other material inputs, while fertilisers and pesticides contribute mainly along the intensive margin, enhancing production conditional on existing capacity.

5.1.2 Productivity dynamics conditional on capacity

Since the estimated IDF separates variable inputs from quasi-fixed inputs, productivity can be interpreted as a residual component capturing changes that are not explained by observed outputs, chemical inputs, or capacity conditions. This allows us to distinguish improvements in performance from adjustments driven by scale expansion or input intensification.

Figure 3 presents the development of country-level productivity indices normalized to a base year, 2009. Productivity is constructed from the estimated log-productivity component of the model and therefore reflects performance changes conditional on outputs, variable inputs, and capacity constraints. As expected, the figure reveals substantial heterogeneity in productivity dynamics across EU member states. While some countries exhibit improvements over time, others display stagnation, pronounced fluctuations, or even decline in productivity. We do not observe a common patterns for EU-wide productivity trend.

These findings indicate that productivity constitutes a distinct margin of adjustment in EU agriculture. In contrast to the scale properties discussed in the previous section, changes in productivity are not driven by capacity expansion or greater chemical input intensity. Instead, they reflect shifts in performance that vary considerably across countries and over time.

Figure 3: Productivity dynamics in EU agriculture

Figure 4 relates average productivity growth to short-run returns to scale (SRTS) and the elasticities of aggregate capacity. The results reveal no systematic relationship between productivity growth and either SRTS or capacity. In particular, countries with high SRTS do not necessarily experience faster productivity growth, and strong capacity effects are not associated with higher productivity performance. This suggests that productivity improvements cannot be assumed to offset the short-run adjustment costs associated with reductions in fertiliser and pesticide use, which we consider in the following section.

Figure 4: Productivity, scale, and capacity

5.1.3 Sensitivity of output to fertiliser and pesticide reductions

We study output sensitivity to fertiliser and pesticide reductions using two standardized scenarios representing moderate and stronger decreases in chemical input use. In Scenario 1, fertilisers and pesticides are reduced by up to 10% for farms exceeding an intensity threshold, while Scenario 2 imposes reductions of up to 20%. The analysis is conducted for the most recent observation year (2021), which serves as a representative baseline for comparing production responses across countries. Quasi-fixed inputs (land, labour, and capital) are held constant; thus, the results capture short-run adjustment effects.

Counterfactual output responses to input restrictions are derived using the estimated IDF. Outputs are normalized to fix output composition, and the model is evaluated at baseline and counterfactual input levels. The implied output change is obtained from the difference in predicted logarithmic distance values, representing a radial adjustment of output consistent with the estimated technology.

The results indicate considerable heterogeneity in output responses across EU member states. Proportional reductions in chemical inputs produce differing production effects, reflecting variation in agricultural systems in their ability to accommodate reductions in input intensity. Increasing the reduction from 10% to 20% strengthens output responses. This implies limited substitution possibilities in the short-run, implying limited substitution possibilities in the short run. These

findings are consistent with the evidence presented in previous sections. Fertilisers and pesticides primarily operate along an intensity margin, while land, labour, and capital condition the scope for adjustment. Consequently, short-run production responses are governed less by the level of chemical input use itself and more by underlying capacity conditions.

5.2 Case studies of technology impacts in the Czech Republic and Germany

5.2.1 Organic farming

This section presents the short-run production structure of organic and conventional farms in the Czech Republic and Germany. Specifically, we focus on the first-order properties of the short-run multi-output production of cereals, milk, and meat. The complete set of parameters is presented in the Appendix (cereals estimates are reported in Tables [A11](#) and [A14](#), milk estimates are reported in Tables [A12](#) and [A15](#), meat estimates are reported in [A13](#) and [A16](#)).

Table [3](#) shows the differences in the first-order properties of the IDF for organic and conventional cereal production in the Czech Republic and Germany, obtained from an estimation with dummy variables for organic farming. This specification is used because the number of observations for organic farms specializing in field crop production is too low to allow reliable separate estimations for organic and conventional farms.

Table 3: Short-run output and input elasticities for organic and conventional cereal production

Country		Czech Republic		Germany	
Contracted work in capital		Organic farming	Conventional farming	Organic farming	Conventional farming
Output Elasticities	yC	-0.081	-0.088***	-0.144*	-0.131***
	$yAOC$	-0.258***	-0.193***	-0.305**	-0.288***
	$yAOO$	-0.021***	-0.010***	-0.044**	-0.031***
SRTS		2.773	3.442	2.030	2.221
Variable Input Elasticities	xF	0.113***	0.119***	0.139***	0.138***
	xP	0.107***	0.110***	0.100***	0.103***
	xO	0.780	0.771	0.761	0.760
Quasi Fixed Input Elasticities	xL	-0.241*	-0.315***	-0.113***	-0.184***
	xW	-0.216	-0.187***	-0.145	-0.131***
	xK	-0.008**	-0.054***	-0.077	-0.042***
Contracted work in material		Organic farming	Conventional farming	Organic farming	Conventional farming
Output Elasticities	yC	-0.084	-0.091***	-0.146**	-0.130***
	$yAOC$	-0.236	-0.204***	-0.312***	-0.296***
	$yAOO$	-0.024***	-0.012***	-0.051***	-0.035***
SRTS		2.908	3.267	1.965	2.171
Variable Input Elasticities	xF	0.115***	0.119***	0.136***	0.136***
	XP	0.026	0.026***	0.014***	0.017***
	xO	0.859	0.855	0.851	0.847
Quasi Fixed Input elasticities	xL	-0.255*	-0.315***	-0.130**	-0.184***
	xW	-0.222	-0.187***	-0.163	-0.131***
	xK	-0.041	-0.054***	-0.072**	-0.042***

With respect to output elasticities, although the production structure remains unchanged, characterized by the highest responsiveness of other crop and livestock output and the lowest responsiveness of other output, organic farming is found to considerably influence output elasticities. This effect is statistically significant at the 5% level for German farms, regardless of how contracted work

is incorporated into the IDF, i.e. whether it is treated as part of capital or materials. In the case of Czech farms, a statistically significant change at the 5% level is observed in both specifications only for other output.

In terms of input elasticities, the results are consistent across both specifications in both countries at the 5% significance level: the Czech sample exhibits a statistically significant decrease in fertiliser elasticity, whereas the German sample shows a statistically significant reduction in pesticide elasticity. With respect to quasi-fixed inputs, both countries show a decrease in land elasticity, with organic farming significantly reducing the elasticity of land; however, in the case of the Czech Republic, the effect is statistically significant only at the 10% level. This result holds regardless of how contracted work is incorporated into the IDF. The increase in labour elasticity observed in both countries and in both specifications is not statistically significant. In contrast, the change in capital elasticity, which differs in direction between the Czech Republic and Germany, is statistically significant at the 5% level, but only in one of the specifications considered. Overall, the results suggest that the changes in elasticities are more pronounced for quasi-fixed inputs than for variable inputs, indicating that organic farming is primarily associated with differences in capacity constraints related to quasi-fixed factors.

Table 4 presents a comparison of production elasticities for organic and conventional milk production in the Czech Republic and Germany. While in Germany, where organic farming is more strongly oriented towards milk production than in the Czech Republic, milk shows the highest marginal responsiveness among the analysed outputs in organic production, in conventional farming and in the Czech Republic the highest responsiveness is associated with other crop and livestock output. Other output exhibits the weakest responsiveness in both countries and under both management types. This conclusion remains valid even when contracted work is included in material instead of capital.

Variable input elasticities show similar patterns in both countries and under both types of management. Output is most strongly affected by the residual category of other material, which is used for normalization, regardless of whether contracted work is included in materials or in capital. Elasticities of quasi-fixed inputs are not statistically significant in the case of Czech organic dairy-oriented farms. In the case of German farms, they are negative in both organic and conventional farming, which suggests that these inputs act as capacity shifters. The relative importance of quasi-fixed inputs differs across model specifications depending on the treatment of contracted work. When contracted work is included in materials, land has the highest elasticity among the quasi-fixed inputs in both organic and conventional farming, whereas capital has the lowest. When contracted work is included in capital, the elasticity of capital becomes the largest and that of land the smallest, but only in conventional farming. In organic farming, land remains the most influential quasi-fixed input.

Tables 5 present the short-run output and input elasticities for meat production in organic and conventional farming in the Czech Republic, where cattle and sheep breeding represent the

Table 4: Short-run output and input elasticities for organic and conventional milk production

Country		Czech Republic		Germany	
Contracted work in capital		Organic farming	Conventional farming	Organic farming	Conventional farming
Output Elasticities	$yMLK$	-0.153***	-0.240***	-0.185***	-0.198***
	$yAOC$	-0.275***	-0.261***	-0.125***	-0.244***
	$yAOO$	0.001	-0.009***	-0.022***	-0.001
SRTS		2.345	1.961	3.007	2.263
Variable Input Elasticities	xFD	0.058***	0.057***	0.088***	0.094***
	xSM	0.233***	0.235***	0.155***	0.208***
	xO	0.709	0.709	0.757	0.699
Quasi Fixed Input Elasticities	xL	-0.065	-0.118***	-0.152***	-0.076***
	xW	-0.101	-0.039	-0.094***	-0.090***
	xK	-0.029	-0.012	-0.088***	-0.119***
Contracted work in material		Organic farming	Conventional farming	Organic farming	Conventional farming
Output Elasticities	$yMLK$	-0.160***	-0.243***	-0.206***	-0.239***
	$yAOC$	-0.265***	-0.266***	-0.139***	-0.244***
	$yAOO$	0.000	-0.010***	-0.024***	-0.003***
SRTS		2.355	1.926	2.711	2.060
Variable Input Elasticities	xFD	0.056***	0.055***	0.083***	0.089***
	xSM	0.228***	0.229***	0.146***	0.196***
	xO	0.715	0.716	0.771	0.716
Quasi Fixed Input Elasticities	xL	-0.075	-0.126***	-0.149***	-0.103***
	xW	-0.105	-0.013	-0.090***	-0.082***
	xK	-0.042	-0.015	-0.073***	-0.064***

dominant specialization of organic farms. The results show that, in both management types and under both specifications depending on the treatment of contracted work, other crop and livestock output exhibits the strongest marginal responsiveness, while other output shows the weakest.

Table 5: Short-run output and input elasticities for organic and conventional meat production

Czech Republic		Contracted work in capital		Contracted work in material	
		Organic farming	Conventional farming	Organic farming	Conventional farming
Output Elasticities	yM	-0.098***	-0.110***	-0.090***	-0.108***
	$yAOC$	-0.202***	-0.200***	-0.205***	-0.208***
	$yAOO$	-0.005***	-0.006**	-0.004***	-0.008***
SRTS		3.284	3.154	3.339	3.087
Variable Input Elasticities	xFD	0.043***	0.035***	0.042***	0.034***
	xSM	0.241***	0.261***	0.235***	0.255***
	xO	0.716	0.774	0.808	0.779
Quasi Fixed Input Elasticities	xL	-0.225***	-0.275***	-0.231***	-0.278***
	xW	-0.103***	-0.201**	-0.095***	-0.195**
	xK	-0.027*	-0.026	-0.033*	-0.035

Similarly to milk production, feed and other specific inputs adjust mainly along the intensive margin, while most of the short-run adjustment required for output expansion is absorbed by the residual category of other material. These conclusions hold regardless of the management type or the treatment of contracted work. The estimated elasticities of quasi-fixed inputs are negative. Consistent with the previous specializations, quasi-fixed inputs in meat production behave as capacity shifters, that reduce the variable input requirements for a given output vector. Among the quasi-fixed inputs, land exhibits the highest elasticity in both organic and conventional farming, regardless of whether contracted work is included in capital or in materials. This suggests that contracted work has only a limited role as a channel through which new technologies enter the

production process.

5.2.2 Precision agriculture

This section presents the short-run production structure of precision agriculture in the Czech Republic. Based on farm-level data for holdings specialized in field crop production, technological differences between farms using precision agriculture technologies and those that do not are evaluated. Owing to the limited number of observations for farms adopting precision agriculture, the analysis of differences is based on dummy variables, which are used to examine variations in the first-order parameters of the IDF.

These first-order properties of the short-run IDF are reported in Table 6. The complete set of estimated parameters is provided in the Appendix (Tables A17 and A18).

Table 6: Short-run output and input elasticities for precision and conventional cereals production

Czech Republic	Parameter	Type of Farming	
		Precision	Conventional
Output Elasticities	yC	-0.198	-0.084***
	$yAOC$	-0.287***	-0.144***
	$yAOO$	-0.015	-0.017***
SRTS		2.001	4.067
Variable Input Elasticities	xSM	0.023	0.020***
	xM	0.046***	0.047***
	xO	0.931	0.934
Quasi Fixed Input Elasticities	xL	-0.056	-0.216***
	xW	0.041*	-0.087
	xK	-0.065	-0.064**

Given that not all variables are available in the Czech FADN dataset, the IDF is specified using the following variable inputs: xSM (specific material), xM (other material), and xO (farming overheads). Statistically significant differences at the 10% level are observed only for the elasticities of other crop output, livestock output, and labour. The adoption of precision agriculture technologies increases the elasticities of other crop and livestock outputs, while the elasticity of labour becomes positive.

Although the results indicate that precision agriculture technologies influence input and output elasticities, the limited number of observations implies that these findings should be considered preliminary, and the analysis needs to be replicated using updated data with a larger number of observations for farms adopting precision agriculture technologies.

6 Discussion

This study evaluates the role of fertilisers and pesticides in European agriculture within a capacity conditioned framework. In this respect, it departs from earlier strands of the literature, which have predominantly relied on partial equilibrium models (Bremmer et al., 2021) and general equilibrium models (Beckman et al., 2020). By contrast, the framework adopted here provides a conceptually and methodologically distinct perspective on the implications of reducing agrochemical inputs.

The contribution most closely related to this approach is Cechura et al. (2025), who analyse the effects of fertilisers and pesticides on output growth and TFP in Czech cereal production using a flexible production function with endogenous inputs. Consistent with the findings presented here, their results point to the dominant role of other material inputs among variable factors of production and land among quasi-fixed inputs. In addition, within the subset of studies focusing on individual EU Member States, Jost et al. (2025) examines the impacts of fertiliser reductions on Austrian agriculture, while Buttinelli et al. (2025) assesses the effects of reductions in both fertilisers and pesticides in Italian agriculture within an integrated agro-economic modelling framework.

All of these studies are oriented toward the ex-ante evaluation of the European Farm-to-Fork Strategy and therefore employ a range of policy scenarios designed to simulate reductions in agrochemical input use and their sectoral implications. In operationalizing these policy targets, the studies specify several alternative reduction pathways.

For instance, Bremmer et al. (2021) assess: (i) a 50% reduction in the overall use of hazardous pesticides; (ii) a 20% reduction in fertiliser use; and (iii) a combined scenario integrating both measures alongside the allocation of at least 10% of agricultural land to high-diversity landscape features. The scenarios specified by Beckman et al. (2020) are broader in scope and include, inter alia, a 50% reduction in agricultural imports. Central to their analysis is a 20% reduction in fertiliser application across all crops, implemented through the introduction of a fertiliser tax. Jost et al. (2025) focus on mineral nitrogen fertilisation, evaluating both a standalone 20% reduction in mineral nitrogen use and a combined scenario coupling this reduction with a maximum application rate of 175 kg N per hectare for crops (excluding temporary grassland) and a complete prohibition of mineral nitrogen fertiliser use on permanent grassland. Finally, Cechura et al. (2025) analyse three input-reduction scenarios: (i) a 10% reduction in overall fertiliser use; (ii) a combined reduction of 10% in fertilisers and 20% in pesticides; and (iii) a 20% reduction in both inputs

Across these studies, a consistent conclusion emerges: reductions in fertiliser and pesticide use are associated with declines in crop yields and overall agricultural production. Fertiliser restrictions are estimated to reduce crop production by approximately 3.5% to 15%, with the most pronounced impacts observed in cereal crops, while constraints on pesticide use are projected to result in production declines ranging from 4.2% to 23%.

These findings reflect the fact that fertilisers and pesticides operate primarily along the intensity margin of agricultural production. As a result, policies aimed at reducing agrochemical use may

generate short-run adjustment costs for agricultural producers, particularly where production systems are tightly conditioned by existing technological and structural constraints. In such contexts, input-reduction targets may initially translate into productivity losses before adaptive responses fully materialize.

The resulting contraction in agricultural output would tighten crop availability in EU markets, placing upward pressure on agricultural commodity prices and increasing the Union’s reliance on imports (Beckman et al., 2020). At the same time, these adjustments are expected to intensify pressure on agricultural land resources, not only within the EU but also in third countries, reflecting potential land-use displacement effects (Bremmer et al., 2021).

The results of this study underscore the structural constraints shaping agricultural adjustment. In particular, the dominant role of quasi-fixed inputs, most notably land, as capacity shifters indicates that farms’ ability to respond to agrochemical reduction targets is mediated by existing factor endowments and production structures. Because land represents an inherently limited resource, adjustment pathways based on extensification remain constrained, thereby reinforcing the importance of technological change and productivity-enhancing innovations as compensatory mechanisms.

Within the broader context, Pandey and Pandey (2023); Fontaine et al. (2024); Bremmer et al. (2021) argue that meeting the projected increase in global food demand will be difficult without a fundamental redesign of current agricultural systems. Such a transition requires enhanced plant–soil synchronization, supported by the integrated deployment of precision and smart agricultural technologies alongside advances in biotechnology. These innovations not only contribute to yield improvements but also generate positive spillovers for soil health and the long-term productive capacity of agricultural systems. Accordingly, agricultural policy should prioritize sustained investment in research and development while facilitating the effective diffusion of technological innovations at the farm level.

At the same time, the substantial heterogeneity observed across European agricultural systems complicates this transition. Differences in production structures, resource endowments, and technological readiness shape both the costs of adjustment to agrochemical reduction targets and farms’ capacity to adopt alternative production practices. As a result, uniform policy instruments may generate uneven outcomes across countries and farm types, reinforcing the need for differentiated transition pathways.

The capacity to adopt these technologies, therefore, remains unevenly distributed. As emphasized by Žáková Kroupová et al. (2026), small and medium-sized farms face disproportionately high barriers to the adoption of capital-intensive precision agriculture technologies. At the same time, they are more strongly affected by agrochemical input reduction policies, as demonstrated by Buttinelli et al. (2025). Addressing these disparities requires targeted financial instruments, including subsidies, concessional loans, and dedicated investment grants, to lower entry costs and mitigate liquidity and investment constraints.

Financial support alone, however, is unlikely to be sufficient. Institutional arrangements that

enable collective adoption represent an additional lever for facilitating technological transition. Encouraging cooperation through farmer groups, machinery-sharing schemes, or agricultural cooperatives allows smaller farms to pool resources, share precision agriculture technologies, and distribute implementation costs. Such collaborative models expand access to innovation while enabling participants to capture economies of scale, thereby contributing to a reduction in persistent productivity disparities between small and large farms (Žáková Kroupová et al., 2026).

Finally, as further noted by Bremmer et al. (2021), strengthening farmers' human capital constitutes a critical complementary pillar of this transition. Targeted training programs, advisory services, and participation in farmer knowledge networks enhance managerial capabilities, accelerate technology adoption, and improve farm-level decision-making. Taken together, financial, institutional, and knowledge-based policy instruments form an integrated framework necessary for scaling sustainable productivity growth under tightening environmental constraints.

7 Conclusions

Agriculture in the European Union is fundamentally shaped by the Common Agricultural Policy. Its current strategic vision emphasizes the importance of fostering a competitive and sustainable agricultural sector through enhanced fairness, policy simplification, and more precisely targeted interventions. The effective design of such measures requires a comprehensive understanding of the factors that shape production possibilities, as well as the drivers of agricultural productivity. This study seeks to provide an empirical foundation for more informed agricultural policy design.

The objectives of this study were twofold. First, we examined the short-run production structure of EU agriculture, with particular attention to capacity constraints arising from quasi-fixed inputs. Second, we analysed productivity dynamics conditional on output, variable inputs (especially fertilisers and pesticides), and farm capacity. In addition, we examined the economic effects of selected agrochemical-saving technologies identified in the FADN database, namely organic farming and precision agriculture, in order to obtain empirical information for the parameterisation of these technologies in terms of their production characteristics. We further evaluated the role of contract work as a channel through which new technologies are incorporated into the production process.

To achieve these objectives, we developed a capacity-conditioned framework for multiple-output, multiple-input agricultural production that allows for consistent estimation and interpretation of elasticities and short-run scale properties, as well as systematic comparison of capacity characteristics. We then empirically applied this framework to agricultural producers in 24 EU Member States and the United Kingdom over the period 2008–2021.

The framework uses an input distance function to model agricultural technology and examine short-run production under capacity constraints arising from land, labour, and capital, while accounting for endogeneity. The results show considerable heterogeneity across European agricultural systems and a clear separation between scale and intensity margins. Fertilisers and pesticides

primarily improve production along the intensive margin rather than contributing to proportional output growth.

These results help clarify the distinct roles of variable and quasi-fixed inputs in shaping short-run production outcomes. By contrast to fertilisers and pesticides, quasi-fixed inputs play a central role in determining short-run production possibilities across EU agriculture. In particular, land emerges as the dominant capacity shifter, reducing the volume of variable inputs required to produce a given output vector. This capacity effect, however, operates within the context of substantial cross-country heterogeneity in structural conditions and factor endowments.

Productivity dynamics, driven primarily by performance shifts rather than capacity expansion or changes in chemical input intensity, also display considerable heterogeneity across European countries. No systematic relationship is observed between productivity growth and either scale expansion or capacity building. Consequently, productivity gains alone are unlikely to offset the short-run adjustment costs associated with reductions in fertiliser and pesticide use.

The results further indicate that the adoption of new technologies modifies short-run input and output elasticities. These effects are not uniform but vary according to production specialization and production conditions. In addition, the impact of contract work is found to be farm-type specific, indicating that outsourced services may act as a substitute for own inputs in some production systems, while in others they serve as a complementary channel facilitating the adoption of new technologies.

These findings have important policy implications. First, since fertilisers and pesticides operate primarily along the intensive margin, policies aimed at reducing agrochemical use are likely to generate short-run adjustment costs, particularly in systems constrained by existing technological and structural conditions. Second, the dominant role of quasi-fixed inputs—especially land—as capacity shifters suggests that the ability of farms to comply with input-reduction targets will depend on their structural characteristics and factor endowments. Third, the pronounced heterogeneity across European agricultural systems implies that uniform policy instruments may yield uneven outcomes across countries.

Together, these insights point to the need for targeted and capacity-sensitive policy design, complemented by support for technological innovation and capacity-enhancing investments to facilitate a sustainable transition toward lower chemical input use.

References

- Ackerberg, D., C. Lanier Benkard, S. Berry, and A. Pakes (2007). Chapter 63 econometric tools for analyzing market outcomes. Volume 6 of *Handbook of Econometrics*, pp. 4171–4276. Elsevier.
- Ackerberg, D. A., K. Caves, and G. Frazer (2015a). Identification properties of recent production function estimators. *83*(6), 2411–2451.

- Akerberg, D. A., K. Caves, and G. Frazer (2015b). Identification properties of recent production function estimators. *Econometrica* 83(6), 2411–2451.
- Bates, D. M. and J. M. Chambers (1992). Nonlinear models. In *Statistical Models*, Wadsworth & Brooks/Cole, Chapter 10. Springer.
- Bates, D. M. and D. G. Watts (1988). *Nonlinear Regression: Iterative Estimation and Linear Approximations*, Chapter 2, pp. 32–66. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Beaumelle, L., L. Tison, N. Eisenhauer, J. Hines, S. Malladi, C. Pelosi, L. Thouvenot, and H. R. P. Phillips (2023). Pesticide effects on soil fauna communities—a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 60(7), 1239–1253.
- Beckman, J., M. Ivanic, J. L. Jelliffe, F. G. Baquedano, and S. G. Scott (2020). Economic and food security impacts of agricultural input reduction under the european union green deal’s farm to fork and biodiversity strategies. Report, United States Department of Agriculture, Washington, USA.
- Biagini, L., F. Antonioli, and S. Severini (2023). The impact of cap subsidies on the productivity of cereal farms in six european countries: A historical perspective (2008–2018). *Food Policy* 119, 102473.
- Bremmer, J., A. R. G. Martinez, R. A. Jongeneel, H. F. Huiting, and R. Stokkers (2021). Impact assessment study on EC 2030 green deal targets for sustainable food production: Effects of farm to fork and biodiversity strategy 2030 at farm, national and EU level. Other, Wageningen, Netherlands.
- Buttinelli, R., G. Dono, and R. Cortignani (2025). Assessing the impacts of chemicals reduction on arable farms through an integrated agro-economic model. *Agricultural Systems* 224, 104254.
- Caves, D. W., L. R. Christensen, and W. E. Diewert (1982). The economic theory of index numbers and the measurement of input, output, and productivity. *Econometrica* 50(6), 1393–1414.
- Cechura, L., A. Grau, H. Hockmann, I. Levkovych, and Z. Kroupova (2017). Catching up or falling behind in european agriculture: The case of milk production. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 68(1), 206–227.
- Cechura, L., S. C. Kumbhakar, and Z. Kroupová (2025). The role of pesticides and fertilizers in czech cereal output and TFP growth: A flexible production function with endogenous inputs. *Food Policy* 136, 102955.
- Chambers, R. G. (1988). *Applied Production Analysis: A Dual Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Coelli, T. J., D. S. P. Rao, C. J. O'Donnell, and G. E. Battese (2005). *An Introduction to Efficiency and Productivity Analysis* (2 ed.). New York, NY: Springer.
- European Commission (2025, February). A Vision for Agriculture and Food: Shaping Together an Attractive Farming and Agri-Food Sector for Future Generations. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions.
- Florens, J.-P. and L. Simar (2005). Parametric approximations of nonparametric frontiers. *Journal of Econometrics* 124(1), 91–116.
- Fontaine, S., L. Abbadie, M. Aubert, S. Barot, J. M. G. Bloor, D. Derrien, O. Duchene, N. Gross, L. Henneron, X. L. Roux, N. Loeuille, J. Michel, S. Recous, D. Wipf, and G. Alvarez (2024). Plant–soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: Learning from ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems. *Global Change Biology* 30(1), e17034.
- Gandhi, A., S. Navarro, and D. A. Rivers (2020). On the identification of gross output production functions. *Journal of Political Economy* 128(8), 2973–3016.
- Greene, W. (2005). Reconsidering heterogeneity in panel data estimators of the stochastic frontier model. *Journal of Econometrics* 126(2), 269–303. Current developments in productivity and efficiency measurement.
- Guo, C., X. Liu, and X. He (2022). A global meta-analysis of crop yield and agricultural greenhouse gas emissions under nitrogen fertilizer application. *Science of The Total Environment* 831, 154982.
- Jost, E., M. Schönhart, H. Mitter, O. Zoboli, and E. Schmid (2025). Integrated modelling of fertilizer and climate change scenario impacts on agricultural production and nitrogen losses in austria. *Ecological Economics* 227, 108398.
- Kellermann, M. and K. Salhofer (2014). Dairy farming on permanent grassland: Can it keep up? *Journal of Dairy Science* 97(10), 6196–6210.
- Kumbhakar, S. C. and C. A. K. Lovell (2000). *Stochastic Frontier Analysis*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kumbhakar, S. C., L. Orea, A. Rodríguez-Álvarez, and E. G. Tsionas (2007). Do we estimate an input or an output distance function? an application of the mixture approach to european railways. *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 27(2), 87–100.
- Latruffe, L., B. E. Bravo-Ureta, A. Carpentier, Y. Desjeux, and V. H. Moreira (2017). Subsidies and technical efficiency in agriculture: Evidence from european dairy farms. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 99(3), 783–799.

- Levinsohn, J. and A. Petrin (2003). Estimating production functions using inputs to control for unobservables. *The Review of Economic Studies* 70(2), 317–341.
- Mahmood, H., M. S. Hassan, G. Meraj, and M. Furqan (2024). Agriculture’s role in environmental sustainability: A comprehensive review of challenges and solutions. *Challenges in Sustainability*, 178–189.
- Mairesse, J., P. Mohnen, and A. Notten (2025). Innovation and productivity: the recent empirical literature and the state of the art. *Eurasian Business Review* 15(1), 1–23. Received: 13 July 2024, Revised: 26 January 2025, Accepted: 31 January 2025, Published: 25 February 2025.
- Malikov, E. and G. Lien (2021). Proxy variable estimation of multiproduct production functions. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 103(5), 1878–1902.
- Malikov, E., S. Zhao, S. C. Kumbhakar, and D. H. B. and (2025). Estimating production functions using costs when outputs are restricted. *Econometric Reviews* 44(4), 433–461.
- Marschak, J. and W. H. Andrews (1944). Random simultaneous equations and the theory of production. *Econometrica* 12(3/4), 143–205.
- Mary, S. (2013). Assessing the impacts of Pillar 1 and 2 subsidies on TFP in French crop farms. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 64(1), 133–144.
- Moré, J. J. (1978). The levenberg-marquardt algorithm: Implementation and theory. In G. A. Watson (Ed.), *Numerical Analysis*, pp. 105–116. Springer.
- Olley, G. S. and A. Pakes (1996). The dynamics of productivity in the telecommunications equipment industry. *Econometrica* 64(6), 1263–1297.
- Pandey, P. C. and M. Pandey (2023). Highlighting the role of agriculture and geospatial technology in food security and sustainable development goals. *Sustainable Development* 31(5), 3175–3195.
- Parven, A., I. M. Meftaul, K. Venkateswarlu, and M. Megharaj (2025). Herbicides in modern sustainable agriculture: environmental fate, ecological implications, and human health concerns. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 22(2), 1181–1202.
- Petrack, M. and M. Kloss (2018, Jun). Identifying agricultural factor productivity from micro-data: A review of approaches with an application to eu countries. *German Journal of Agricultural Economics* (670-2021-576).
- Polemis, M. L. and M. G. Tsionas (2022). Endogenous productivity: a new bayesian perspective. *Annals of Operations Research* 318, 425–451. Published online: 09 January 2022, Accepted: 22 December 2021.
- Shephard, R. (1953). *Cost and Production Functions*. Princeton University Press.

- Shephard, R. W. (1970). *Theory of Cost and Production Functions*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- StataCorp (2023). *Stata 18 Base Reference Manual*. College Station, TX: Stata Press.
- Tey, Y. S. and M. Brindal (2015). *Factors Influencing Farm Profitability*, pp. 235–255. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Tyagi, J., S. Ahmad, and M. Malik (2022). Nitrogenous fertilizers: impact on environment sustainability, mitigation strategies, and challenges. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 19(11), 11649–11672.
- Wimmer, S. and R. Finger (2025). Productivity dispersion and persistence in european agriculture. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*.
- Zhengfei, G., A. Oude Lansink, M. van Ittersum, and A. Wossink (2006). Integrating agronomic principles into production function specification: A dichotomy of growth inputs and facilitating inputs. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 88(1), 203–214.
- Žáková Kroupová, Z., L. Rumánková, B. Bajan, L. Čechura, Z. Hloušková, R. Aulová, P. Šimek, and J. Jarolímek (2026). Drivers and barriers to precision agriculture adoption in czech agriculture. *Precision Agriculture* 27(1), 17.

Appendix

Table A1: Descriptive Statistics

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Austria	Cereal Output	6538	37411.71	28121.62	224.4	164512.8
	Other Crop Output	6538	42727	59584.38	0	1306548
	Other output	6538	33677.46	47478.05	0	1002679
	Fertilisers	6538	5829.13	5857.44	0	79534.84
	Pesticides	6538	4467.82	4665.85	0	49500
	Other Materials	6538	46654.34	38870.3	4535.52	908550.4
	Area	6538	57.08	34.5	3.38	263
	Labour	6538	1.42	1	0.04	12.82
	Capital	6538	3326.26	2300.16	0.02	25558.61
Belgium	Cereal Output	3049	44665.16	29525.32	445.93	152381.5
	Other Crop Output	3049	109231.8	135152.3	0	1738673
	Other output	3049	78519.23	98058.3	0	1120178
	Fertilisers	3049	14051.22	11116.17	0	119303.4
	Pesticides	3049	16924.58	16296.14	0	242158.1
	Other Materials	3049	99324.19	83486.14	5055.5	652881.6
	Area	3049	83.11	47.09	11.78	323.4
	Labour	3049	1.76	0.95	0.01	15.15
	Capital	3049	7033.85	6537.85	14.31	61864.23
Bulgaria	Cereal Output	11281	227018.6	301854	35.05	1763643
	Other Crop Output	11281	149794.8	201229.5	0	2658230
	Other output	11281	26826.82	105898.5	0	1924561
	Fertilisers	11281	55759.85	77809.93	0	1264610
	Pesticides	11281	37270.19	54304.25	0	664372.3
	Other Materials	11281	152025.6	205246.1	400.37	2415496
	Area	11281	637.78	715.28	0.39	9098.2
	Labour	11281	11.64	16.71	0.11	928
	Capital	11281	4649.76	8560.93	1.08	144454.7
Czechia	Cereal Output	9600	230896.3	285536.8	189.92	1773502
	Other Crop Output	9600	258262.3	387728.1	0	4532374
	Other output	9600	378213.3	714252.1	0	6701993
	Fertilisers	9600	74822.84	98564.76	0	769987.4
	Pesticides	9600	72980.07	95339.37	0	796845.8

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Czechia	Other Materials	9600	572758.8	873235.2	2374.69	7790259
	Area	9600	717.53	841.18	6.46	4975.87
	Labour	9600	18.21	26.19	0.2	227.83
	Capital	9600	15561.03	24631.98	2.92	282214.2
Denmark	Cereal Output	7336	128190.3	134822.9	903.41	795874
	Other Crop Output	7336	129193.9	222423.9	0	3388155
	Other output	7336	177934.5	305485.4	0	5941904
	Fertilisers	7336	30154.75	35202.33	0	383964.1
	Pesticides	7336	18253.84	23213.1	0	234737.9
	Other Materials	7336	207647.5	248209.8	6121.64	4011837
	Area	7336	222.47	215.17	2.9	1644.16
	Labour	7336	2.04	2.13	0.09	47.99
	Capital	7336	36215.46	37736.57	0	441188.9
Estonia	Cereal Output	3225	80611.04	112920	13.77	674138.8
	Other Crop Output	3225	55394.23	109563.8	0	1352590
	Other output	3225	54131.53	186891.6	0	2635629
	Fertilisers	3225	37334.7	60254.38	0	544004.4
	Pesticides	3225	14748.14	25173.57	0	282955.7
	Other Materials	3225	103793.1	201808.3	372.49	2708411
	Area	3225	344.51	431.57	1.72	6985.29
	Labour	3225	2.65	4.32	0.01	58.02
	Capital	3225	3812.16	6538.32	1.43	62088.61
Finland	Cereal Output	3064	25638.2	22343.68	151.41	130585.7
	Other Crop Output	3064	14410.15	35137.13	0	516613
	Other output	3064	20233.06	42286.54	0	684029.5
	Fertilisers	3064	8152.64	8083.12	0	74505.9
	Pesticides	3064	4004.77	4871.23	0	39982.43
	Other Materials	3064	49284.68	50486.39	3879.46	617820.9
	Area	3064	87.69	60.68	11.43	415.9
	Labour	3064	0.9	0.7	0.04	7.4
	Capital	3064	4162.92	3098.13	149.54	20197.7
France	Cereal Output	28842	83005.65	56447.44	183.45	303892.4
	Other Crop Output	28842	66822.39	119153.9	0	3208986
	Other output	28842	50931.58	79150.86	0	1093780
	Fertilisers	28842	24075.38	16610.93	0	182675.7

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
France	Pesticides	28842	22457.54	18087.49	0	330591.3
	Other Materials	28842	91112.88	80088.13	2318.05	1517574
	Area	28842	143.19	85.11	8.04	740
	Labour	28842	1.86	1.55	0.03	42.32
	Capital	28842	2732.66	2299.31	0.34	34882.94
Germany	Cereal Output	38779	108442.3	168423.3	194.25	1272044
	Other Crop Output	38779	102971.9	191512.1	0	4536140
	Other output	38779	124317.8	399476.1	0	15500000
	Fertilisers	38779	29994.01	49561.77	0	620144.2
	Pesticides	38779	25234.23	40632.29	0	454390.4
	Other Materials	38779	170571.1	366931.3	3966.69	9025644
	Area	38779	212.41	349.3	4.81	4030.65
	Labour	38779	3.17	6.81	0.11	210.37
Greece	Capital	38779	10152.68	12386.52	0.01	243994.2
	Cereal Output	20407	8924.94	10468.11	12	67415.73
	Other Crop Output	20407	18757.08	23510.1	0	443798.6
	Other output	20407	2637.21	9705.64	0	471896
	Fertilisers	20407	3711.82	3616.02	0	66244.35
	Pesticides	20407	2455.85	3322.26	0	88408.64
	Other Materials	20407	14210.26	12261.93	259.97	222298.1
	Area	20407	24.3	21.2	0.2	350
Hungary	Labour	20407	1.2	0.93	0.01	19.83
	Capital	20407	1402.41	1270.63	0.6	15971.77
	Cereal Output	15351	83217.32	136349	68.84	1042861
	Other Crop Output	15351	58272.54	133120.2	0	6779099
	Other output	15351	50323.58	226294.9	0	7230954
	Fertilisers	15351	19921.21	36618.83	0	465212.8
	Pesticides	15351	15001.87	32141.15	0	592914.7
	Other Materials	15351	97826.05	285947.4	743.55	12000000
Ireland	Area	15351	208.4	332.45	0.4	4629
	Labour	15351	3.83	8.54	0.01	231.65
	Capital	15351	3293.81	6074.22	0.15	336034.3
	Cereal Output	1039	42205.98	46339.2	353.75	497796.7
	Other Crop Output	1039	18362.58	44684.35	0	931867
	Other output	1039	26651.97	30527.16	0	232803.5

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Ireland	Fertilisers	1039	14494.04	13948.45	0	137463.1
	Pesticides	1039	9341.65	12746.33	0	179993.9
	Other Materials	1039	43918.71	36365.18	3342.39	334819.1
	Area	1039	77.52	57.27	6.69	493.12
	Labour	1039	1.27	0.78	0.01	6.71
	Capital	1039	14995.68	10038.33	93.85	72750.51
Italy	Cereal Output	33898	24843.2	34818.35	40.89	253500
	Other Crop Output	33898	34718.85	99699.26	0	3758040
	Other output	33898	8638.61	54133.57	0	2024924
	Fertilisers	33898	6209.67	10384.26	0	316439.4
	Pesticides	33898	4003.85	8555.96	0	375159.9
	Other Materials	33898	27130.85	52248.79	170.65	1789824
	Area	33898	43.74	52.08	1	796.53
	Labour	33898	1.49	1.46	0.02	41.62
Capital	33898	5211.11	15363.75	0.35	2188009	
Latvia	Cereal Output	5651	89245.3	125562.6	28.18	823659.4
	Other Crop Output	5651	43746.41	82513.38	0	882725.6
	Other output	5651	39958.79	142580	0	1808987
	Fertilisers	5651	32269.42	51164.82	0	547441.2
	Pesticides	5651	14858.99	26719.7	0	368771
	Other Materials	5651	78523.73	146136.3	966.25	2213462
	Area	5651	256.1	305.72	2.67	2125.01
	Labour	5651	3.67	7.08	0.12	118.07
Capital	5651	2990.54	5545.68	1.21	73459.8	
Lithuania	Cereal Output	7131	90346.15	134256.1	40.04	962146.6
	Other Crop Output	7131	58947.88	111625.6	0	1619829
	Other output	7131	23700.16	122784.8	0	2465386
	Fertilisers	7131	36952.65	60704.25	0	673904.9
	Pesticides	7131	15778.04	27875.04	0	311164.3
	Other Materials	7131	58161.43	122296.6	979.64	2409676
	Area	7131	224.7	289.42	2.25	3784.31
	Labour	7131	3.3	6.14	0.39	130.54
Capital	7131	3220.21	5425.05	5.68	129844.3	
Luxemburg	Cereal Output	433	38298.51	34120.37	1637.11	174272
	Other Crop Output	433	43571.46	70896.31	0	896099.6

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Luxemburg	Other output	433	82160.31	128846.2	125.85	931056.8
	Fertilisers	433	12003	11007.64	0	69698.41
	Pesticides	433	10482	10042.2	0	66554.38
	Other Materials	433	87292.34	113175.4	9507.17	626986
	Area	433	93.06	60.3	24.27	302.91
	Labour	433	1.44	0.99	0.2	8.71
	Capital	433	8734.6	6577.51	292.89	51237.68
Netherlands	Cereal Output	2871	41700.77	46328.15	0	372486.1
	Other Crop Output	2871	313435.9	374882.8	0	4308320
	Other output	2871	115976.1	214693.7	0	2389048
	Fertilisers	2871	17054.09	16947.5	0	173636
	Pesticides	2871	42374.22	51265.93	0	645487.4
	Other Materials	2871	204680.5	229502.7	11324.22	2631743
	Area	2871	96.66	87.67	2.05	912.15
	Labour	2871	2.2	2.19	0.1	21.78
Capital	2871	42418.55	47245.75	81.09	540942.5	
Poland	Cereal Output	77722	18725.5	30292.39	23.67	326170.7
	Other Crop Output	77722	17966.1	43900.69	0	2311067
	Other output	77722	10381.79	36477.9	0	2176680
	Fertilisers	77722	7219.77	13398.28	0	435038.6
	Pesticides	77722	3666.39	8468.1	0	290839.2
	Other Materials	77722	19587.54	42383.43	741.86	1952939
	Area	77722	48.25	73.76	0.37	2126
	Labour	77722	1.91	1.86	0.04	62.79
Capital	77722	2646.21	3110.96	2.12	61010.41	
Portugal	Cereal Output	2359	15030.56	22892.74	6.75	133153.3
	Other Crop Output	2359	25818.26	84634.76	0	1553178
	Other output	2359	5574.22	13654.36	0	201820.1
	Fertilisers	2359	3946.23	9629.85	0	232871
	Pesticides	2359	3518.45	11706.66	0	314739
	Other Materials	2359	18360.21	37743.09	228.55	610166.7
	Area	2359	48.42	99.12	0.84	1058
	Labour	2359	1.73	1.22	0.04	14.5
Capital	2359	913.49	1511.55	0.11	15370.97	
Romania	Cereal Output	30992	71620.36	126745.2	19.5	890213.1

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Romania	Other Crop Output	30992	54292.57	126341.4	0	3712982
	Other output	30992	4637.15	29878.79	0	1201296
	Fertilisers	30992	16947.28	33157.42	0	439961.7
	Pesticides	30992	9594.74	20407.96	0	508107.9
	Other Materials	30992	47183.32	86572.77	195.73	1552421
	Area	30992	222.48	388.51	0.15	5056
	Labour	30992	3.11	4.73	0.04	120.82
	Capital	30992	1489.59	4255.96	0.1	252552.5
Slovakia	Cereal Output	4426	249058.4	326690.3	412.18	1873768
	Other Crop Output	4426	227292.8	371950.6	0	5175458
	Other output	4426	244858	489018.4	0	4781481
	Fertilisers	4426	67773.29	90004.55	0	809638.3
	Pesticides	4426	65109.73	93386.95	0	741357.6
	Other Materials	4426	447926.3	661899.4	3584	6007441
	Area	4426	702.57	841.3	8.69	5161.06
	Labour	4426	16.01	23.4	0.09	224.13
Slovenia	Capital	4426	7208.24	11454.53	0.37	160234.8
	Cereal Output	1600	4618.34	4308.94	17.46	19754.49
	Other Crop Output	1600	10993.66	19843.34	0	195458
	Other output	1600	7748.31	10183.04	0	71806.37
	Fertilisers	1600	1609.13	2472.98	0	58929.53
	Pesticides	1600	1038.7	1937.06	0	20614.46
	Other Materials	1600	14607.79	13839.48	1724.98	111368
	Area	1600	12.39	8.18	1.92	57.59
Spain	Labour	1600	1.43	1.07	0.1	10.44
	Capital	1600	1722.46	1635.34	19.47	18463.4
	Cereal Output	29587	31164.69	29499.23	73.38	193466
	Other Crop Output	29587	22510.06	58269.75	0	2629323
	Other output	29587	5163.42	23989.55	0	1210883
	Fertilisers	29587	7815.67	8867.88	0	250932.8
	Pesticides	29587	3980.16	6880.11	0	203706.9
	Other Materials	29587	24924.15	33860.16	563.15	1523522
Spain	Area	29587	89.34	85.51	2.42	1501
	Labour	29587	1.4	1.51	0.01	72.14
	Capital	29587	2602.65	4281.08	0.05	239749

Country	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Sweden	Cereal Output	3275	70510.98	87896.35	473.03	566549.1
	Other Crop Output	3275	65669.21	212016.1	0	6364515
	Other output	3275	52369.51	86325.5	0	1099212
	Fertilisers	3275	20461.58	26220.13	0	289036.8
	Pesticides	3275	10609.62	16678.49	0	216782.8
	Other Materials	3275	104993	155923.3	5423.95	3558333
	Area	3275	151.32	166.65	17.9	2671.9
	Labour	3275	1.44	2.15	0.06	60.9
	Capital	3275	10819.24	13054.05	10.3	160827.6
United Kingdom	Cereal Output	9033	118474.1	107101.6	797.64	760016.1
	Other Crop Output	9033	107098.7	275630.2	0	7521034
	Other output	9033	80050.76	124741.4	0	1991529
	Fertilisers	9033	36230.92	34887.13	0	334893.5
	Pesticides	9033	31025.26	37550.76	0	606068.9
	Other Materials	9033	151994.4	182060.7	5599.14	3249749
	Area	9033	225.08	193.34	13.6	2873.62
	Labour	9033	2.48	4.14	0.01	189.47
	Capital	9033	27263.76	30484.72	0.01	313144.1

Table A2: Results of the First Step NLSUR Estimation

Fertilisers Cost Share Equation							
Parameter	Austria	Belgium	Bulgaria	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland
<i>const.</i>	0.094***	0.114***	0.215***	0.12***	0.116***	0.169***	0.118***
<i>f</i>	0.014***	0.023***	0.044***	0.023***	0.019***	0.033***	0.016***
<i>h</i>	0.000	-0.019***	-0.014***	0.003***	-0.014***	-0.013***	0.005***
<i>a</i>	0.018***	0.028***	0.012***	0.015***	0.013***	0.023***	0.014***
<i>w</i>	-0.016***	-0.008***	-0.019***	-0.017***	-0.003***	-0.012***	-0.013***
<i>k</i>	0.008***	-0.016***	0.001	-0.004***	0.004***	-0.009***	0.000
<i>t</i>	-0.003***	-0.001***	0.001***	0.000	-0.001***	-0.001***	0.000
<i>c</i>	-0.003***	-0.001	0.007***	0.01***	-0.004***	0.015***	0.005***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.003***	-0.003***	0.003***	0.000**	0.001***	0.002***	-0.002***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.012***	-0.009***	-0.002***	-0.004***	-0.015***	-0.008***	-0.003***
Pesticides Cost Share Equation							
Parameter	Austria	Belgium	Bulgaria	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland
<i>const.</i>	0.059***	0.123***	0.101***	0.11***	0.076***	0.05***	0.052***
<i>h</i>	0.01***	0.023***	0.018***	0.021***	0.012***	0.021***	0.007***
<i>f</i>	0.001***	-0.003***	0.000***	0.004***	-0.006***	-0.006***	0.002**
<i>a</i>	0.02***	-0.005***	0.003***	0.009***	0.002***	-0.007***	-0.001
<i>l</i>	0.000	-0.011***	0.000	-0.013***	0.001	0.005***	-0.007***
<i>k</i>	-0.005***	-0.002***	0.000	-0.004***	0.003***	0.004***	0.004**
<i>t</i>	-0.001***	0.001***	0.002***	0.000***	0.000***	0.001***	0.000**
<i>c</i>	-0.004***	0.008***	0.001***	0.01***	0.008***	0.003***	0.006***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.001***	0.011***	0.002***	0.002***	0.001***	0.001***	0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.006***	-0.009***	0.000**	-0.005***	-0.009***	-0.004***	0.000

Table A3: Results of the First Step NLSUR Estimation (2nd Part)

Fertilisers Cost Share Equation							
Parameter	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia
<i>const.</i>	0.185***	0.131***	0.172***	0.15***	0.201***	0.157***	0.168***
<i>f</i>	0.032***	0.012***	0.043***	0.034***	0.132***	0.031***	0.023***
<i>h</i>	-0.021***	0.005***	-0.012***	-0.011***	-0.001	-0.007***	-0.006***
<i>a</i>	0.015***	0.014***	0.025***	0.01***	0.004**	-0.002***	-0.008***
<i>w</i>	-0.017***	0.001*	0.005***	-0.006***	-0.002	0.001**	-0.01***
<i>k</i>	0.000	0.000	-0.003***	0.001***	0.002**	0.002***	0.008***
<i>t</i>	-0.001***	0.002***	-0.002***	0.001***	-0.002***	-0.001***	0.002***
<i>c</i>	0.005***	-0.002***	0.003***	0.003***	-0.003***	0.004***	0.025***
<i>aoc</i>	0.002***	0.000***	-0.004***	0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	0.000
<i>aoo</i>	-0.013***	-0.015***	0.000***	-0.002***	0.000*	-0.001***	-0.007***
Pesticides Cost Share Equation							
Parameter	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia
<i>const.</i>	0.135***	0.099***	0.08***	0.096***	0.105***	0.069***	0.064***
<i>h</i>	0.02***	0.012***	0.017***	0.02***	0.036***	0.013***	0.011***
<i>f</i>	-0.003***	0.000***	-0.004***	-0.005***	-0.001	-0.006***	-0.001***
<i>a</i>	0.011***	0.003***	-0.003***	0.000	-0.014***	0.006***	0.007***
<i>l</i>	0.007***	0.000	0.011***	0.004***	0.000	-0.008***	0.002
<i>k</i>	-0.001***	0.002***	0.004***	0.003***	-0.002**	-0.001***	0.005***
<i>t</i>	0.000**	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	0.000***	0.000***	0.002***
<i>c</i>	-0.001***	0.008***	-0.003***	-0.001*	0.016***	0.002***	-0.005***
<i>aoc</i>	0.002***	-0.001***	0.001***	0.001***	0.003***	0.000**	0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.01***	-0.006***	-0.001***	-0.002***	-0.003***	-0.001***	-0.003***

Table A4: Results of the First Step NLSUR Estimation (3rd Part)

Fertilisers Cost Share Equation							
Parameter	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Netherland	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Slovakia
<i>const.</i>	0.226***	0.132***	0.073***	0.149***	0.101***	0.175***	0.13***
<i>f</i>	0.037***	0.066***	0.015***	0.015***	0.016***	0.041***	0.029***
<i>h</i>	0.002***	-0.025***	-0.01***	0.01***	-0.002	-0.016***	0.005***
<i>a</i>	0.025***	0.021***	0.014***	0.001*	0.000	0.019***	0.002**
<i>w</i>	-0.008***	-0.002	-0.001*	-0.011***	0.000	0.000	-0.009***
<i>k</i>	-0.004***	-0.008**	-0.005***	-0.002***	0.000	0.005***	-0.002***
<i>t</i>	-0.001***	-0.001**	0.000***	0.000***	0.000	-0.002***	-0.001***
<i>c</i>	0.004***	-0.002	0.000***	0.01***	0.000	-0.014***	0.004***
<i>aoc</i>	0.002***	-0.001	-0.002***	0.001***	0.000	0.001***	0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.007***	-0.002	-0.008***	-0.002***	0.000	-0.004***	-0.003***
Pesticides Cost Share Equation							
Parameter	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Netherland	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Slovakia
<i>const.</i>	0.088***	0.083***	0.135***	0.08***	0.086***	0.097***	0.098***
<i>h</i>	0.017***	0.014***	0.013***	0.01***	0.013***	0.02***	0.016***
<i>f</i>	-0.006***	0.003*	-0.009***	0.001***	0.000	-0.003***	0.008***
<i>a</i>	-0.002***	0.009*	0.035***	-0.007***	-0.001	0.013***	0.002***
<i>l</i>	0.005***	0.012***	-0.019***	-0.003***	0.000	0.004***	-0.004***
<i>k</i>	0.006***	-0.013***	-0.007***	0.008***	0.000	0.001***	-0.001***
<i>t</i>	0.001***	0.001***	0.001***	-0.001***	0.001	0.000***	-0.001***
<i>c</i>	0.000	0.016***	-0.001***	0.002***	0.002	-0.012***	0.007***
<i>aoc</i>	0.002***	0.003***	0.002***	0.002***	0.000	0.000	0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.004***	-0.004**	-0.018***	-0.002***	0.000	-0.002***	-0.001***

Table A5: Results of the First Step NLSUR Estimation (4th Part)

Fertilisers Cost Share Equation				
Parameter	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
<i>const.</i>	0.071***	0.208***	0.141***	0.154***
<i>f</i>	0.012***	0.041***	0.019***	0.03***
<i>h</i>	0.000	-0.011***	0.012***	0.01***
<i>a</i>	0.031***	0.01***	0.026***	0.022***
<i>w</i>	0.000	-0.003***	-0.015***	0.001
<i>k</i>	-0.012***	-0.004***	-0.003***	-0.001***
<i>t</i>	0.000	-0.004***	-0.002***	-0.003***
<i>c</i>	0.004***	0.016***	0.011***	-0.005***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.004***	0.002***	-0.001*	-0.004***
<i>aoa</i>	-0.003***	-0.003***	-0.014***	-0.004***
Pesticides Cost Share Equation				
Parameter	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
<i>const.</i>	0.041***	0.065***	0.048***	0.121***
<i>h</i>	0.01***	0.014***	0.015***	0.016***
<i>f</i>	-0.001***	-0.003***	-0.002***	0.006***
<i>a</i>	0.005***	0.000	0.001	0.003***
<i>l</i>	0.001	0.000**	0.004***	0.000
<i>k</i>	0.001	0.002***	-0.004***	0.008***
<i>t</i>	0.001***	0.001***	-0.001***	0.000***
<i>c</i>	0.002***	0.003***	0.004***	0.011***
<i>aoc</i>	0.001***	0.001***	0.001***	0.003***
<i>aoa</i>	-0.002***	0.000***	-0.002***	-0.009***

Table A6: Results of the Second Step - Non-Linear Mixed Effects Regression (1st Part)

Parameter	Austria	Belgium	Bulgaria	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland
<i>R</i>	-0.069***	0.021	-0.073***	-0.035***	-0.026***	-0.099***	-0.035***
<i>a</i>	-0.419***	-0.49***	-0.466***	-0.285***	-0.381***	-0.313***	-0.294***
<i>l</i>	-0.091***	-0.165***	-0.06***	-0.148***	-0.227***	-0.071***	-0.153***
<i>k</i>	-0.054***	-0.036***	-0.042***	-0.077***	-0.075***	-0.045**	-0.138***
<i>t</i>	0.006***	-0.004***	-0.003**	-0.011***	0.011***	-0.017***	0.001
<i>c</i>	-0.053***	-0.068***	-0.117***	-0.106***	-0.056***	-0.221***	-0.076***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.074***	-0.15***	-0.098***	-0.125***	-0.061***	-0.103***	-0.031***
<i>aoa</i>	-0.112***	-0.135***	-0.005***	-0.057***	-0.129***	-0.053***	-0.078***
<i>aa</i>	-0.271***	0.101	0.001	-0.051	-0.174***	-0.105*	0.069
<i>ll</i>	-0.117***	-0.126**	-0.013	-0.04**	-0.165***	-0.087**	-0.02
<i>kk</i>	-0.056***	-0.016	-0.006***	-0.011***	-0.004*	-0.001	-0.101**
<i>tt</i>	0.002***	0.002***	0.008***	0.002***	0.000	0.000	0.000
<i>cc</i>	-0.029**	0.005	-0.023**	-0.012	-0.006	-0.056***	0.001
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.013***	-0.021***	-0.017***	-0.012***	-0.008***	-0.017***	-0.006***
<i>aoaao</i>	-0.032***	-0.02***	-0.006***	-0.011***	-0.019***	-0.014***	-0.015***
<i>axw</i>	0.07***	0.184***	0.009	0.107***	0.202***	0.094***	-0.054
<i>ark</i>	0.083***	0.064**	-0.01	0.054***	0.022	-0.007	0.074
<i>lax</i>	-0.018	-0.083***	-0.006	-0.048***	-0.015	-0.001	-0.009
<i>cxao</i>	0.004	0.061***	0.021***	0.026***	0.013***	0.011***	0.01***
<i>cxaoa</i>	0.023***	0.012***	-0.002**	0.000	0.013**	0.023***	-0.005
<i>aocxao</i>	0.004***	0.01***	0.002***	0.001***	0.000	0.003***	0.001*
<i>cxax</i>	0.035	-0.068**	-0.017	-0.034**	0.025	-0.032	-0.108***
<i>cxal</i>	-0.012	0.003	0.031***	0.023**	-0.029	0.037*	0.071***
<i>cxk</i>	-0.026**	-0.008	0.011**	-0.002	-0.01	0.017	0.017
<i>aocxa</i>	0.008	-0.063***	-0.003	-0.016***	-0.028***	-0.005	-0.011**
<i>aocxl</i>	-0.006	0.01	0.000	-0.016***	0.009***	-0.004	-0.007**
<i>aoxxk</i>	-0.006	0.02*	-0.003***	-0.004***	0.008**	0.000	0.006
<i>aooxa</i>	0.026***	-0.002	0.012***	0.007***	0.006	0.01	0.032***
<i>aooxl</i>	-0.007	-0.008*	-0.006***	-0.002*	-0.017***	-0.034***	-0.008
<i>aooxk</i>	-0.003	0.001	-0.002***	0.000	0.000	-0.014***	-0.012*
<i>axt</i>	0.007***	-0.012***	-0.004*	-0.001	0.006	-0.004	0.005
<i>lxt</i>	-0.004**	-0.005	-0.001	-0.005***	-0.005*	-0.001	0.003
<i>kxt</i>	0.000	0.002	-0.003***	-0.005***	0.000	0.006**	-0.007*
<i>cxt</i>	-0.001	0.006***	0.003*	0.005***	-0.002	0.000	0.003
<i>aocxt</i>	-0.003***	-0.006***	0.002***	0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.001
<i>aooxt</i>	-0.002***	-0.001***	0.001***	0.000	0.001*	-0.001	0.000
<i>meana</i>	0.107***	0.025	-0.074***	-0.159***	0.096***	-0.203***	0.049
<i>meanl</i>	-0.129***	-0.102**	-0.054***	-0.104***	-0.252***	0.006	-0.114***
<i>meank</i>	-0.144***	-0.075***	-0.038***	0.005	0.031**	0.02	-0.143***

Table A7: Results of the Second Step - Non-Linear Mixed Effects Regression (2nd Part)

Parameter	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia
<i>R</i>	-0.016***	-0.065***	-0.093***	-0.04***	-0.187***	-0.108***	-0.09***
<i>a</i>	-0.44***	-0.314***	-0.369***	-0.434***	-0.447***	-0.259***	-0.333***
<i>l</i>	-0.059***	-0.103***	-0.168***	-0.124***	-0.056	-0.081***	-0.105***
<i>k</i>	-0.05***	-0.016***	-0.058***	-0.021***	-0.024	-0.023***	-0.067***
<i>t</i>	-0.012***	0.005***	-0.007***	0.003***	-0.012***	-0.008***	-0.019***
<i>c</i>	-0.108***	-0.144***	-0.135***	-0.178***	-0.148***	-0.249***	-0.226***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.058***	-0.123***	-0.12***	-0.072***	-0.067***	-0.176***	-0.093***
<i>aoa</i>	-0.056***	-0.134***	-0.003*	-0.03***	-0.052***	-0.013***	-0.052***
<i>aa</i>	0.015	-0.017	0.083***	0.13***	0.247*	0.125***	-0.115***
<i>ll</i>	-0.066***	-0.05***	0.064***	-0.029***	-0.13*	-0.037***	-0.112***
<i>kk</i>	-0.01***	-0.005***	-0.005	0.004*	-0.045	0.001	-0.013*
<i>tt</i>	0.003***	-0.001***	0.005***	0.004***	0.001	0.006***	0.000
<i>cc</i>	-0.006	-0.043***	-0.047***	-0.019***	0.112***	-0.048***	-0.083***
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.009***	-0.017***	-0.016***	-0.011***	-0.01*	-0.028***	-0.016***
<i>aoaao</i>	-0.011***	-0.023***	-0.003***	-0.01***	-0.008***	-0.003***	-0.013***
<i>axw</i>	0.036***	0.048***	0.000	0.014	-0.101	-0.001	0.096***
<i>ark</i>	-0.003	-0.007	-0.01	-0.01	0.139***	0.002	-0.012
<i>lzk</i>	-0.008*	-0.007	-0.029***	-0.031***	0.058	-0.005	-0.015
<i>cxao</i>	0.006***	0.032***	0.019***	0.019***	0.077***	0.026***	0.014***
<i>cxaoa</i>	0.025***	0.006***	-0.006***	-0.001	0.027***	0.003***	0.006**
<i>aocxao</i>	0.003***	0.003***	0.002***	0.000**	0.003*	0.001**	0.001***
<i>cx</i>	-0.047***	-0.011	-0.001	-0.057***	-0.157**	-0.021***	0.03
<i>cxl</i>	0.045***	0.018**	0.01**	0.05***	0.118***	0.066***	0.032**
<i>cxk</i>	0.01***	0.021***	0.016***	0.013***	-0.073*	0.006**	0.024**
<i>aocxa</i>	-0.001	-0.018***	-0.003**	-0.02***	-0.084***	-0.013***	-0.006*
<i>aocxl</i>	0.001	0.000	-0.016***	0.007***	-0.015	-0.004**	-0.004
<i>aocxk</i>	0.000	-0.001	-0.002*	0.003***	-0.02	0.001	0.000
<i>aooxa</i>	-0.003	0.024***	0.011***	0.01***	-0.026***	0.007***	0.005
<i>aooxl</i>	-0.01***	-0.015***	-0.004***	-0.008***	0.011*	-0.006***	-0.008***
<i>aooxk</i>	-0.004***	0.001	0.003***	0.000	-0.011***	0.000	0.004**
<i>axt</i>	0.003***	0.000	0.001	0.006***	-0.014*	0.002	-0.005*
<i>lxt</i>	-0.001**	0.001	0.002*	-0.006***	0.018***	-0.008***	0.001
<i>kxt</i>	-0.002***	-0.002***	0.001	0.002***	-0.002	0.002***	0.003*
<i>cxt</i>	-0.001**	-0.001	0.001	-0.007***	-0.006	0.002**	0.002
<i>aocxt</i>	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	0.006**	-0.001***	0.000
<i>aooxt</i>	-0.001***	0.000	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001**	0.000	0.001**
<i>meana</i>	0.025*	0.000	-0.07***	-0.017	-0.103	-0.032**	-0.12***
<i>meanl</i>	-0.289***	-0.101***	-0.037***	-0.158***	0.008	-0.249***	0.001
<i>meank</i>	-0.033***	-0.037***	-0.029**	0.027***	0.012	-0.004	-0.008

Table A8: Results of the Second Step - Non-Linear Mixed Effects Regression (3rd Part)

Parameter	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Netherland	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Slovakia
<i>R</i>	-0.141***	-0.069	-0.047***	-0.038***	-0.096***	-0.071***	-0.042***
<i>a</i>	-0.364***	-0.247*	-0.464***	-0.388***	-0.14***	-0.548***	-0.301***
<i>l</i>	-0.079***	-0.055	-0.062***	-0.101***	-0.15***	-0.089***	-0.106***
<i>k</i>	-0.047***	-0.15**	-0.072***	-0.082***	-0.059***	-0.029***	-0.029***
<i>t</i>	-0.011***	-0.008**	-0.015***	0.001***	-0.009***	0.001*	-0.017***
<i>c</i>	-0.199***	-0.219***	-0.002	-0.134***	-0.255***	-0.14***	-0.142***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.133***	-0.102***	-0.172***	-0.073***	-0.094***	-0.088***	-0.09***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.022***	-0.188***	-0.087***	-0.063***	-0.033***	-0.021***	-0.045***
<i>aa</i>	0.037	-0.096	-0.131**	0.128***	0.155***	0.059***	-0.003
<i>ll</i>	-0.088***	0.114	-0.038	0.034***	-0.035	-0.022**	-0.089***
<i>kk</i>	-0.054***	-0.083	-0.052***	-0.018***	0.000	0.000	-0.003
<i>tt</i>	-0.001	0.001	0.004***	0.007***	0.002**	0.003***	0.002***
<i>cc</i>	-0.027**	-0.136**	0.003**	-0.008**	-0.013	0.033***	-0.01
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.021***	-0.014***	-0.035***	-0.01***	-0.017***	-0.013***	-0.012***
<i>aoao</i>	-0.014***	-0.062***	-0.012***	-0.015***	-0.003	0.000	-0.009***
<i>axw</i>	0.025	0.051	0.031	-0.048***	-0.048	0.029***	0.104***
<i>axk</i>	0.035*	-0.034	0.062**	0.007	-0.017	-0.004	0.008
<i>lwk</i>	-0.018	-0.057	-0.015	-0.009	0.001	-0.019***	-0.02***
<i>cxao</i>	0.019***	-0.02	0.013***	0.024***	0.009***	0.018***	0.012***
<i>cxao</i>	0.006***	-0.017	0.014***	-0.001***	0.008***	-0.001	0.002
<i>aocxao</i>	0.002***	-0.01	0.01	0.002***	0.000	0.001***	0.001***
<i>cx</i>	-0.061***	0.15	-0.008**	-0.051***	-0.03**	-0.066***	-0.009
<i>cxl</i>	0.053***	-0.018	-0.014***	0.032***	0.063***	0.014**	-0.006
<i>cxk</i>	0.022**	0.144**	-0.009***	0.032***	0.003	0.013***	0.012***
<i>aocxa</i>	-0.001	0.019	-0.029	-0.015***	-0.002	-0.007***	-0.006
<i>aocxl</i>	-0.003	0.000	0.033*	-0.004***	-0.006	-0.008***	-0.006**
<i>aoxxk</i>	-0.002	0.018	0.023**	-0.003***	0.000	0.002***	0.001
<i>aooxa</i>	0.003	-0.094*	0.032***	0.01***	0.007**	0.008***	0.000
<i>aooxl</i>	0.001	-0.008	-0.047***	0.000	0.002	-0.002**	0.002
<i>aooxk</i>	-0.001	0.013	-0.01*	0.000	-0.003*	-0.003***	0.001
<i>axt</i>	0.000	-0.016	-0.004	-0.005***	-0.007***	-0.011***	-0.003
<i>lxt</i>	-0.006**	0.019*	0.000	0.007***	-0.008	-0.003**	0.007***
<i>kxt</i>	-0.003	-0.01	-0.004***	0.004***	0.004**	0.001	-0.001
<i>cxt</i>	0.006***	0.000	0.000	-0.003***	0.002	0.012***	0.004**
<i>aocxt</i>	0.000	0.005*	-0.003*	0.000***	0.000	0.001***	0.001
<i>aooxt</i>	0.000	0.002	0.005***	0.000	0.000	-0.002***	-0.001**
<i>meana</i>	-0.012	-0.003	0.088**	-0.047***	-0.182***	0.025***	-0.144***
<i>meanl</i>	-0.064***	-0.071	-0.36***	-0.18***	-0.415***	-0.038***	-0.13***
<i>meank</i>	-0.025	-0.004	0.038	-0.096***	0.05*	-0.024***	-0.005

Table A9: Results of the Second Step - Non-Linear Mixed Effects Regression (4th Part)

Parameter	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
<i>R</i>	-0.06***	-0.105***	-0.006	-0.019***
<i>a</i>	-0.274***	-0.247***	-0.228***	-0.278***
<i>l</i>	-0.006	-0.053***	-0.132***	-0.131***
<i>k</i>	-0.012	-0.074***	-0.007	-0.077***
<i>t</i>	0.004	-0.014***	-0.001	-0.011***
<i>c</i>	-0.135***	-0.313***	-0.133***	-0.179***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.077***	-0.101***	-0.12***	-0.118***
<i>aoa</i>	-0.121***	-0.013***	-0.088***	-0.07***
<i>aa</i>	0.293**	0.018	-0.053	0.02
<i>ll</i>	0.04	0.095***	-0.14***	-0.135***
<i>kk</i>	-0.031	-0.012***	-0.013**	-0.013***
<i>tt</i>	0.002	0.005***	0.008***	0.004***
<i>cc</i>	0.017	-0.068***	-0.021	-0.019*
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.009***	-0.02***	-0.018***	-0.014***
<i>aoaoao</i>	-0.023***	-0.001	-0.016***	-0.011***
<i>axw</i>	-0.078	-0.006	0.084**	0.079***
<i>axk</i>	0.017	0.011*	0.004	0.028***
<i>lzk</i>	0.022	-0.024***	-0.018	0.007
<i>cxaoa</i>	0.019***	0.014***	0.014***	0.034***
<i>cxaoa</i>	0.004	0.004***	-0.002	0.008***
<i>aocxaoa</i>	0.003***	0.001***	-0.001	0.001*
<i>cxk</i>	-0.076**	0.013**	-0.04	-0.038**
<i>cxl</i>	0.008	0.01	0.053**	0.023**
<i>cxk</i>	0.041*	0.022***	0.011	-0.013**
<i>aocxa</i>	0.006	0.001	-0.007	-0.023***
<i>aocxl</i>	-0.031***	-0.002	0.000	-0.003
<i>aoxk</i>	-0.003	0.001*	-0.001	0.000
<i>aoxa</i>	-0.001	0.003***	0.024***	0.000
<i>aooxl</i>	-0.001	-0.017***	-0.036***	-0.004***
<i>aooxk</i>	-0.003	0.000	0.007**	-0.001
<i>axt</i>	-0.009	0.004***	-0.005	0.000
<i>lxt</i>	0.004	-0.013***	0.002	-0.001
<i>kxt</i>	0.001	-0.004***	0.002	-0.001
<i>cxt</i>	0.000	0.01***	0.004*	0.002*
<i>aocxt</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.001
<i>aooxt</i>	-0.001	0.000***	-0.001	0.000
<i>meana</i>	-0.129	0.054***	-0.165***	-0.147***
<i>meanl</i>	-0.346***	-0.232***	-0.129***	-0.053***
<i>meank</i>	-0.043	0.004	-0.043**	0.05***

Table A10: Descriptive Statistics

Model	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Contracted Work in Capital Czech Republic Cereal Dummy model	Cereal Output	9,686	258253.2	372420.3	189.92	6300491
	Other Crop Output	9,686	580733.1	922623.1	0	7930116
	Other Output	9,686	98448.4	273295.8	0	4417773
	Fertilisers	9,686	82604.8	118891.9	64.2	2024672
	Pesticides	9,686	79809.73	109983.5	0	1098475
	Other Material	9,686	573703	901405.3	2374.69	7559279
	Area	9,686	760.73	928.17	6.46	10160.26
	Labour	9,686	19.12	27.61	0.2	232.48
	Capital	9,686	1500.54	2172.1	1.48	27034.35
Contracted Work in Material Czech Republic Cereal Dummy model	Cereal Output	9,621	259696.1	373089.7	189.92	6300491
	Other Crop Output	9,621	584394.1	924615	0	7930116
	Other Output	9,621	99079.23	274100.7	0	4417773
	Fertilisers	9,621	83062.27	119059.5	64.2	2024672
	Pesticides	9,621	80239.49	110101.5	0	1098475
	Other Material	9,621	614556.5	944811.3	2374.69	7790259
	Area	9,621	765.13	929.47	6.46	10160.26
	Labour	9,621	19.24	27.67	0.2	232.48
	Capital	9,621	1137.62	1736.68	0.17	21966.04
Contracted Work in Capital Germany Cereal Dummy model	Cereal Output	39,002	130453	260086.7	15.24	5771594
	Other Crop Output	39,002	223068.6	525045.6	0	9895414
	Other Output	39,002	48197.02	238564.1	0	13200000
	Fertilisers	39,002	35275.64	66571.2	0.01	1260659
	Pesticides	39,002	29867.38	56270.89	0	833821.5
	Other Material	39,002	183949.6	455862.7	2521.84	8480003
	Area	39,002	247.42	462.38	4.81	6016.52
	Labour	39,002	3.71	8.62	0.11	210.37
	Capital	39,002	750.88	1434.21	0.05	32536.21
Contracted Work in Material Germany Cereal Dummy model	Cereal Output	38,881	130707.6	260427.4	15.24	5771594
	Other Crop Output	38,881	223575.5	525757.9	0	9895414
	Other Output	38,881	48323.4	238923.2	0	13200000
	Fertilisers	38,881	35346.12	66652.54	0.01	1260659
	Pesticides	38,881	29930.6	56340.09	0	833821.5
	Other Material	38,881	203116.2	483203.2	3829.56	9025644
	Area	38,881	247.85	462.94	4.81	6016.52

Model	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
	Labour	38,881	3.72	8.64	0.11	210.37
	Capital	38,881	555.76	1120.96	0	21584.82
Contracted Work in Capital Czech Republic Organic Farm Milk Production	Milk Output	267	181864.8	219514.6	116.15	1519122
	Other Crop & Animal Output	267	138557.4	203517.8	7230.66	1278543
	Other Output	267	54587.08	188821.1	0	1877344
	Animal Specific Costs	267	39124.8	62355.58	1050.7	471396.5
	Feedingstuffs	267	96299.67	138769	1218.38	736975.5
	Other material	267	292736.5	452865.5	14648.44	3222296
	Area	267	358.43	430.47	17.64	1686.31
	Labour	267	11.21	12.68	1.16	64.16
	Capital	267	736.41	1224.24	40.68	9401.05
	Contracted Work in Capital Czech Republic Conventional Farm Milk Production	Milk Output	1,911	575306.3	638863.5	2295.67
Other Crop & Animal Output		1,911	590590.6	834884	918.68	7990254
Other Output		1,911	154868.1	328560.2	0	3792089
Animal Specific Costs		1,911	181531.6	381744	359.77	4318624
Feedingstuffs		1,911	321564.4	350060.7	857.92	2344189
Other material		1,911	1069108	1312308	3628.8	9783758
Area		1,911	799.48	785.54	1.54	4344.33
Labour		1,911	29.12	29.69	0.7	177.27
Capital		1,911	1862.54	2203.43	1.59	16224.06
Contracted Work in Capital Germany Organic Farm Milk Production		Milk Output	2,636	152581.3	245982	108.23
	Other Crop & Animal Output	2,636	47618.8	140897.6	194.75	3239604
	Other Output	2,636	14541.38	53036.14	0	1078951
	Animal Specific Costs	2,636	23885.99	52992.08	262.6	983280.3
	Feedingstuffs	2,636	40230.11	130465.4	0	2925855
	Other material	2,636	123460.7	293452.2	9453.13	5056757
	Area	2,636	103.81	230.62	13.97	3371.73
	Labour	2,636	2.55	4.81	0.4	83.77
	Capital	2,636	486.57	798.55	8.26	13067.15
	Milk Output	28,175	276407.9	463776.9	23.18	6067206
Other Crop & Animal Output	28,175	129410.4	359903.4	36.52	6654123	

Model	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Contracted Work in Capital Germany Conventional Farm Milk Production	Other Output	28,175	42420.55	292295.6	0	14400000
	Animal Specific Costs	28,175	63356.21	164713.3	38.81	4685122
	Feedingstuffs	28,175	93981.17	195011.8	37.22	3784866
	Other material	28,175	277486.5	652454.1	6408.95	17700000
	Area	28,175	153.48	333.63	1.13	4017.15
	Labour	28,175	3.86	9.4	0.25	135
	Capital	28,175	771.68	1356.82	0.63	21782.37
Contracted Work in Material Czech Republic Organic Farm Milk Production	Milk Output	267	181864.8	219514.6	116.15	1519122
	Other Crop & Animal Output	267	138557.4	203517.8	7230.66	1278543
	Other Output	267	54587.08	188821.1	0	1877344
	Animal Specific Costs	267	39124.8	62355.58	1050.7	471396.5
	Feedingstuffs	267	96299.67	138769	1218.38	736975.5
	Other material	267	304179	472753	14883.71	3363425
	Area	267	358.43	430.47	17.64	1686.31
	Labour	267	11.21	12.68	1.16	64.16
Capital	267	618.24	1020.85	38.11	7761.63	
Contracted Work in Material Czech Republic Conventional Farm Milk Production	Milk Output	1,904	577047.4	639370.8	2295.67	4813258
	Other Crop & Animal Output	1,904	592287.2	835917	918.68	7990254
	Other Output	1,904	155423.6	329035.8	0	3792089
	Animal Specific Costs	1,904	182122.9	382317.6	359.77	4318624
	Feedingstuffs	1,904	322470.5	350349.4	857.92	2344189
	Other material	1,904	1103525	1348219	3628.8	9942953
	Area	1,904	801.43	786.12	1.54	4344.33
	Labour	1,904	29.21	29.71	0.7	177.27
	Capital	1,904	1556.63	1868.82	0.97	10651.26
Contracted Work in Material Germany Organic Farm Milk Production	Milk Output	2,634	152640.7	246065.8	108.23	4515025
	Other Crop & Animal Output	2,634	47608.06	140950.5	194.75	3239604
	Other Output	2,634	14546.11	53055.9	0	1078951
	Animal Specific Costs	2,634	23892.87	53011.58	262.6	983280.3
	Feedingstuffs	2,634	40238.7	130514.5	0	2925855
	Other material	2,634	133843	301816.3	11615.85	5056757
	Area	2,634	103.84	230.71	13.97	3371.73

Model	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
	Labour	2,634	2.55	4.81	0.4	83.77
	Capital	2,634	379.05	711.75	6.41	13067.15
Contracted Work in Material Germany Conventional Farm Milk Production	Milk Output	28,169	276452.9	463815.7	23.18	6067206
	Other Crop & Animal Output	28,169	129434.1	359938	36.52	6654123
	Other Output	28,169	42429.45	292326.1	0	14400000
	Animal Specific Costs	28,169	63366.89	164729.2	38.81	4685122
	Feedingstuffs	28,169	93996.49	195029.6	37.22	3784866
	Other material	28,169	298113.2	675209.2	7255.81	18100000
	Area	28,169	153.51	333.66	1.13	4017.15
	Labour	28,169	3.86	9.4	0.25	135
	Capital	28,169	557.69	1106.84	0.13	17322.01
Contracted Work in Capital Czech Republic Organic Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	1,794	33756.39	45987.41	124.03	567127.1
	Other Crop & Animal Output	1,794	38168	70728.54	662.17	676761.1
	Other Output	1,794	13481.84	39047.68	0	519176.2
	Animal Specific Costs	1,794	6767.77	12023.62	17.16	128796.6
	Feedingstuffs	1,794	33215.42	45144.62	362.22	324169
	Other material	1,794	100779.2	136745.8	4338.04	832420.2
	Area	1,794	248.85	328.97	12.35	2120.57
	Labour	1,794	4.38	6.07	0.21	89.13
	Capital	1,794	304.05	416.62	7.3	3038.7
Contracted Work in Capital Czech Republic Conventional Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	590	31084.18	49083.94	4.42	492702.5
	Other Crop & Animal Output	590	68598.17	175011.4	240.58	1442652
	Other Output	590	13663.99	68610.22	0	1116689
	Animal Specific Costs	590	10725.61	24255.03	126.51	248128.4
	Feedingstuffs	590	38637.5	73804.66	757.15	544515.6
	Other material	590	107982.3	217737.4	6384.25	1486734
	Area	590	180.31	315.39	10.58	2284.94
	Labour	590	3.94	6.94	0.63	51.13
	Capital	590	273.92	477.45	3.23	3524.14
	Meat Output	1,302	48412.01	61856.87	293.63	592818.5
	Other Crop & Animal Output	1,302	23360.27	62879.32	0	723476.3

Model	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Contracted Work in Capital Germany Organic Farm Milk Production	Other Output	1,302	17525.36	49115.71	0	512114.3
	Animal Specific Costs	1,302	8109.34	19244.37	0	229785.5
	Feedingstuffs	1,302	11329.3	33838.72	0	659014.9
	Other material	1,302	71419.86	116622.9	5374.81	1029012
	Area	1,302	186.9	295.46	13.06	2508.63
	Labour	1,302	2.23	3.15	0.35	47.17
	Capital	1,302	392.01	608.67	12.76	7238.51
Contracted Work in Material Germany Conventional Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	7,184	81037.98	98421.46	22.38	1692437
	Other Crop & Animal Output	7,184	65899.71	137718.2	0	3568449
	Other Output	7,184	16085.18	107508.4	0	3668596
	Animal Specific Costs	7,184	16539.8	29631.54	0	555834.6
	Feedingstuffs	7,184	40699.47	65554.35	0	1286263
	Other material	7,184	110523.2	185491.2	2975.6	4237756
	Area	7,184	99.34	170.89	4.93	2615.62
	Labour	7,184	1.85	3.23	0.21	86.59
Capital	7,184	367.12	478.17	3.83	10227.55	
Contracted Work in Material Czech Republic Organic Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	1,791	33790.16	46017.3	124.03	567127.1
	Other Crop & Animal Output	1,791	38220.69	70775.94	662.17	676761.1
	Other Output	1,791	13504.23	39076.55	0	519176.2
	Animal Specific Costs	1,791	11095.43	16772.84	158.14	146689.7
	Feedingstuffs	1,791	33260.83	45168.58	362.22	324169
	Other material	1,791	107300	147701.6	4338.04	1001210
	Area	1,791	249.16	329.16	12.35	2120.57
	Labour	1,791	4.39	6.07	0.21	89.13
	Capital	1,791	240.2	306.11	2.38	2272.23
Contracted Work in Material Czech Republic Conventional Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	1,791	33790.16	46017.3	124.03	567127.1
	Other Crop & Animal Output	1,791	38220.69	70775.94	662.17	676761.1
	Other Output	1,791	13504.23	39076.55	0	519176.2
	Animal Specific Costs	1,791	11095.43	16772.84	158.14	146689.7
	Feedingstuffs	1,791	33260.83	45168.58	362.22	324169
	Other material	1,791	107300	147701.6	4338.04	1001210
	Area	1,791	249.16	329.16	12.35	2120.57

Model	Variable	N	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
	Labour	1,791	4.39	6.07	0.21	89.13
	Capital	1,791	240.2	306.11	2.38	2272.23
Contracted Work in Material Germany Organic Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	1,297	48162.41	61459.5	293.63	592818.5
	Other Crop & Animal Output	1,297	23416.69	62991.7	0	723476.3
	Other Output	1,297	17581.27	49201.73	0	512114.3
	Animal Specific Costs	1,297	10864.32	24339.9	25.73	273258
	Feedingstuffs	1,297	11209.93	33704.4	0	659014.9
	Other material	1,297	83624.64	134525.9	6684.03	1114114
	Area	1,297	186.02	295.05	13.06	2508.63
	Labour	1,297	2.24	3.15	0.35	47.17
	Capital	1,297	261.46	402.29	2.01	6073.88
Contracted Work in Material Germany Conventional Farm Meat Production	Meat Output	7,181	81069.51	98429.91	22.38	1692437
	Other Crop & Animal Output	7,181	65924.64	137741.5	0	3568449
	Other Output	7,181	16090.37	107530.6	0	3668596
	Animal Specific Costs	7,181	16546.47	29635.93	0	555834.6
	Feedingstuffs	7,181	40715.51	65563.34	0	1286263
	Other material	7,181	121970.1	196436.6	3932	4315595
	Area	7,181	99.36	170.92	4.93	2615.62
	Labour	7,181	1.85	3.23	0.21	86.59
	Capital	7,181	248.56	366.61	0.4	8278.96
Precision Farming Czech Republic Cereal Dummy model	Cereal Output	1,276	6057365	10400000	5000	152000000
	Other Crop Output	1,276	7663444	14400000	0	124000000
	Other Output	1,276	2902437	7954409	0	80500000
	Fertilisers	1,276	5453055	8683816	44045.73	98400000
	Pesticides	1,276	2049290	6938678	0	64500000
	Other Material	1,276	5474413	8766914	25510.02	94600000
	Area	1,276	584.43	842.53	9.58	10160.26
	Labour	1,276	10.11	16.29	0.2	136.99
	Capital	1,276	20473.53	35456.38	34.24	563868.3

Table A11: Results of First step NLSUR Cereals Estimation

Contract work in Capital		
Fertilisers Cost Share Equation	CZE	DEU
<i>konst.</i>	0.119***	0.138***
<i>f</i>	0.032***	0.014***
<i>p</i>	0.002***	0.002***
<i>a</i>	0.011***	0.017***
<i>l</i>	-0.009***	0.002***
<i>k</i>	0.003***	-0.017***
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.002***
<i>m</i>	0.001***	0.001***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.007***	-0.009***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000**	0.001***
<i>d_f</i>	-0.006***	0.002***
Pesticides Cost Share Equation	CZE	DEU
<i>konst.</i>	0.11***	0.103***
<i>p</i>	0.026***	0.017***
<i>f</i>	0.000	0.001***
<i>a</i>	0.012***	0.007***
<i>l</i>	-0.009***	-0.006***
<i>k</i>	0.006***	-0.004***
<i>t</i>	0.000***	0.000***
<i>m</i>	0.000***	-0.001***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.006***	-0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.001***	0.000***
<i>d_p</i>	-0.003***	-0.003***
Fertilisers Cost Share Equation	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.119***	0.136***
<i>f</i>	0.031***	0.014***
<i>p</i>	0.004***	0.006***
<i>a</i>	0.018***	0.017***
<i>l</i>	-0.015***	-0.004***
<i>k</i>	-0.001***	-0.013***
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.002***
<i>m</i>	0.000***	0.000***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.005***	-0.008***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000***	0.000***
<i>d_f</i>	-0.004***	-0.001***
Pesticides Cost Share Equation	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.11***	0.103***
<i>p</i>	0.026***	0.017***
<i>f</i>	-0.001	0.001***
<i>a</i>	0.023***	0.007***
<i>l</i>	-0.018***	-0.006***
<i>k</i>	-0.001***	-0.003***
<i>t</i>	-0.001***	0.000
<i>m</i>	-0.001***	-0.001***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.003***	-0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000***	0.000***
<i>d_p</i>	0.000	-0.003***

Table A12: Results of First step NLSUR Milk Estimation

Farming Type	Organic farming		Conventional farming	
	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
Contract work in Capital				
Specific AP Cost				
<i>const.</i>	0.058***	0.088***	0.057***	0.146***
<i>sm</i>	0.032***	0.023***	0.029***	0.015***
<i>fd</i>	-0.017***	-0.008***	-0.013***	0.009***
<i>a</i>	-0.009**	-0.006***	-0.001	0.019***
<i>l</i>	0.004	0.021***	-0.002**	-0.017***
<i>k</i>	0.001	0.005***	-0.001	-0.001
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.001***	-0.002***	-0.003***
<i>m</i>	-0.002***	-0.003***	-0.003***	-0.002***
<i>aoc</i>	0.009***	0.002**	0.008***	-0.013***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000	-0.001***	0.000*	0.002***
Feedingstuffs Cost				
	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.058***	0.088***	0.057***	0.146***
<i>sm</i>	0.032***	0.023***	0.029***	0.015***
<i>fd</i>	-0.017***	-0.008***	-0.013***	0.009***
<i>a</i>	-0.009**	-0.006***	-0.001	0.019***
<i>l</i>	0.004	0.021***	-0.002**	-0.017***
<i>k</i>	0.001	0.005***	-0.001	-0.001
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.001***	-0.002***	-0.003***
<i>m</i>	-0.002***	-0.003***	-0.003***	-0.002***
<i>aoc</i>	0.009***	0.002**	0.008***	-0.013***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000	-0.001***	0.000*	0.002***
Contract work in Material				
Specific AP Cost	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.056***	0.083***	0.055***	0.132***
<i>sm</i>	0.032***	0.022***	0.028***	0.012***
<i>fd</i>	-0.016***	-0.005***	-0.015***	0.008***
<i>a</i>	-0.009**	-0.006***	0.001	0.016***
<i>l</i>	0.004	0.021***	-0.004***	-0.016***
<i>k</i>	-0.001	0.004***	-0.001**	0.001***
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.001***	-0.002***	-0.004***
<i>m</i>	-0.002**	-0.003***	-0.003***	-0.002***
<i>aoc</i>	0.01***	0.002**	0.008***	-0.011***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000	-0.001***	0.000**	0.001***
Feedingstuffs Cost				
	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.228***	0.146***	0.229***	0.104***
<i>fd</i>	0.088***	0.025***	0.031***	0.015***
<i>sm</i>	-0.029***	0.031***	-0.025***	0.004***
<i>a</i>	0.005	-0.02***	0.022***	0.016***
<i>l</i>	0.001	0.02***	-0.006*	-0.016***
<i>k</i>	-0.005	0.009***	-0.003*	-0.002***
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.001***	-0.001*	-0.001***
<i>m</i>	0.000	0.004***	0.001	-0.003***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.003	0.005***	-0.012***	-0.003***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.002***	-0.003***	-0.002***	0.003***

Table A13: Results of First step NLSUR Meat Estimation

Farming Type	Organic farming		Conventional farming	
	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
Contract work in Capital				
Specific AP Cost				
<i>const.</i>	0.043***	0.07***	0.035***	N/A
<i>sm</i>	0.022***	0.02***	0.015***	N/A
<i>fd</i>	-0.009***	-0.006***	-0.019***	N/A
<i>a</i>	0.000	-0.004***	0.003	N/A
<i>l</i>	-0.005***	-0.005**	-0.003*	N/A
<i>k</i>	0.001	0.004***	0.000	N/A
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.001***	N/A
<i>m</i>	0.001	0.003***	-0.003***	N/A
<i>aoc</i>	0.001	0.001***	0.001	N/A
<i>aoo</i>	0.000***	0.000	0.000	N/A
Feedingstuffs Cost				
	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.241***	0.05***	0.261***	N/A
<i>fd</i>	0.099***	0.007***	0.128***	N/A
<i>sm</i>	0.008***	0.008***	-0.021***	N/A
<i>a</i>	-0.01***	-0.006***	0.01***	N/A
<i>l</i>	-0.006***	-0.006***	-0.009***	N/A
<i>k</i>	0.003***	0.006***	0.000	N/A
<i>t</i>	-0.003***	0.001***	-0.001**	N/A
<i>m</i>	0.006***	0.002***	-0.002**	N/A
<i>aoc</i>	0.002**	0.001***	0.002	N/A
<i>aoo</i>	0.001***	0.000	0.000	N/A
Contract work in Material				
Specific AP Cost	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.042***	0.067***	0.034***	N/A
<i>sm</i>	0.021***	0.02***	0.015***	N/A
<i>fd</i>	-0.011***	-0.005***	-0.016***	N/A
<i>a</i>	0.002**	-0.005***	0.003*	N/A
<i>l</i>	-0.006***	-0.003*	-0.003*	N/A
<i>k</i>	0.000	0.003***	-0.001	N/A
<i>t</i>	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.001***	N/A
<i>m</i>	0.000	0.002***	-0.004***	N/A
<i>aoc</i>	0.002**	0.000**	0.001	N/A
<i>aoo</i>	0.000***	0.000	0.000	N/A
Feedingstuffs Cost				
	CZE	DEU	CZE	DEU
<i>const.</i>	0.001***	0.05***	0.255***	N/A
<i>fd</i>	0.001***	0.007***	0.128***	N/A
<i>sm</i>	0.001***	0.008***	-0.02***	N/A
<i>a</i>	0.001***	-0.001	0.008***	N/A
<i>l</i>	0.002	-0.007***	-0.007***	N/A
<i>k</i>	0.001***	-0.001	0.003***	N/A
<i>t</i>	0.000***	0.000	0.000	N/A
<i>m</i>	0.000***	0.001***	-0.002***	N/A
<i>aoc</i>	0.001	0.000***	0.000	N/A
<i>aoo</i>	0.000***	0.000	0.000	N/A

Table A14: Comparison of Results between CZ and DE in Cereals IDF

<i>Est.</i>	Spec. 1		Spec.2	
	CZ	DE	CZ	DE
<i>R</i>	-0.041***	-0.022***	-0.051***	-0.031***
<i>a</i>	-0.315***	-0.184***	-0.328***	-0.198***
<i>l</i>	-0.187***	-0.131***	-0.144***	-0.087***
<i>k</i>	-0.054***	-0.042***	-0.027***	-0.029***
<i>t</i>	-0.009***	0.003***	-0.006***	0.001***
<i>c</i>	-0.088***	-0.131***	-0.091***	-0.13***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.193***	-0.288***	-0.204***	-0.296***
<i>aoo</i>	-0.01***	-0.031***	-0.012***	-0.035***
<i>aa</i>	-0.079***	-0.076***	-0.099***	-0.066***
<i>ll</i>	-0.023	0.054***	-0.049***	0.015
<i>kk</i>	-0.013***	-0.026***	-0.009***	-0.016***
<i>tt</i>	0.002***	-0.001***	0.001***	0.000***
<i>cc</i>	-0.01***	-0.016***	-0.011***	-0.016***
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.02***	-0.04***	-0.021***	-0.041***
<i>aoaoo</i>	-0.004***	-0.004***	-0.004***	-0.005***
<i>arw</i>	0.114***	-0.018**	0.146***	0.012*
<i>ark</i>	0.04***	0.047***	0.036***	0.029***
<i>lwk</i>	-0.03***	0.012*	-0.034***	0.006
<i>craoc</i>	0.025***	0.013***	0.019***	0.014***
<i>craoo</i>	0.001***	0.001***	0.001*	0.001**
<i>aocraoo</i>	0.000	0.002***	0.000	0.002***
<i>cra</i>	-0.005*	0.003	-0.009***	0.003**
<i>cxl</i>	-0.009**	-0.003**	-0.008**	-0.005***
<i>cxk</i>	-0.015***	-0.001	-0.003***	-0.001
<i>aocxa</i>	0.005	0.024***	0.005	0.02***
<i>aocxl</i>	-0.036***	-0.011***	-0.035***	-0.008***
<i>aocxk</i>	-0.005**	0.000	-0.002	0.002**
<i>aooxa</i>	0.000	0.005***	0.000	0.004***
<i>aooxl</i>	0.001	-0.012***	0.002*	-0.011***
<i>aooxk</i>	0.001*	-0.006***	0.000	-0.004***
<i>art</i>	-0.001	0.001*	0.001	0.000
<i>lxt</i>	-0.001	0.001*	-0.003***	0.003***
<i>kxt</i>	-0.001	-0.003***	-0.001	-0.001**
<i>cxt</i>	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
<i>aocxt</i>	0.000	-0.001***	0.000	-0.002***
<i>aooxt</i>	0.000***	0.000**	0.000***	0.000**
<i>meana</i>	-0.053***	-0.008	-0.105***	-0.072***
<i>meanl</i>	-0.079***	-0.05***	-0.092***	-0.046***
<i>meank</i>	-0.065***	-0.126***	-0.029***	-0.05***
<i>Prec_{ca}</i>	0.074*	0.072***	0.059*	0.054**
<i>Prec_{cl}</i>	-0.029	-0.013	-0.035	-0.032
<i>Prec_{ck}</i>	0.046**	-0.035	0.012	-0.03**
<i>Prec_{cc}</i>	0.007	-0.014*	0.007	-0.016**
<i>Prec_{caoc}</i>	-0.065***	-0.016**	-0.033	-0.016***
<i>Prec_{caoo}</i>	-0.012***	-0.012**	-0.012***	-0.016***
<i>Prec_{ct}</i>	0.001	0.015***	0.003	0.011***

Notes: Spec. 1 = Contract work in Capital. Spec. 2 = Contract work in Material.

Table A15: Comparison of Results between CZ and DE in Milk IDF

Type	Organic				Conventional			
	Spec. 1		Spec.2		Spec. 1		Spec. 2	
<i>Est.</i>	CZ	DE	CZ	DE	CZ	DE	CZ	DE
<i>const.</i>	-0.087*	-0.326***	-0.095*	-0.318***	-0.163***	-0.176***	-0.152***	-0.167***
<i>a</i>	-0.065	-0.152***	-0.075	-0.149***	-0.118***	-0.076***	-0.126***	-0.103***
<i>l</i>	-0.101	-0.094***	-0.105	-0.09***	-0.039	-0.09***	-0.013	-0.082***
<i>k</i>	-0.029	-0.088***	-0.042	-0.073***	-0.012	-0.119***	-0.015	-0.064***
<i>t</i>	-0.022***	-0.002*	-0.017***	-0.003**	-0.008***	-0.009***	-0.006***	-0.009***
<i>c</i>	-0.153***	-0.185***	-0.16***	-0.206***	-0.24***	-0.198***	-0.243***	-0.239***
<i>aoc</i>	-0.275***	-0.125***	-0.265***	-0.139***	-0.261***	-0.244***	-0.266***	-0.244***
<i>aoa</i>	0.001	-0.022***	0.000	-0.024***	-0.009***	-0.001	-0.01***	-0.003***
<i>aa</i>	-0.019	0.145***	0.09	0.19***	-0.083**	0.216***	-0.057	0.217***
<i>ll</i>	-0.142	-0.102	-0.01	-0.081	0.01	0.142***	0.011	0.131***
<i>kk</i>	-0.076	0.028	-0.154*	-0.02***	0.000	-0.049***	-0.007	-0.015***
<i>tt</i>	0.006***	0.001**	0.005**	0.001**	0.002***	0.003***	0.002***	0.002***
<i>cc</i>	-0.014**	-0.024***	-0.017***	-0.028***	-0.032***	-0.023***	-0.032***	-0.029***
<i>aocaoc</i>	0.035	-0.047***	-0.005	-0.065***	-0.142***	-0.092***	-0.152***	-0.088***
<i>aoaoa</i>	0.000	-0.004***	0.000	-0.004***	-0.002**	0.001***	-0.002***	0.000
<i>aw</i>	0.298	0.005	0.191	-0.022	0.134***	-0.154***	0.077*	-0.113***
<i>ak</i>	-0.067	-0.022	-0.089	-0.024	0.005	0.031***	-0.002	0.01*
<i>lk</i>	0.049	-0.027	0.081	0.002	-0.072***	0.014*	-0.027	-0.003
<i>cxao</i>	0.085*	0.015***	0.077*	0.009**	0.024***	0.027***	0.024***	0.028***
<i>cxaoa</i>	0.000	0.002*	0.001	0.002*	0.000	0.000**	0.000	0.000***
<i>aocxao</i>	-0.003	0.006	-0.001	0.003	0.007***	0.001	0.005**	0.001
<i>cxao</i>	-0.059	0.004	-0.053	0.000	0.01	-0.003*	0.009	-0.004***
<i>cxl</i>	-0.06	-0.003	-0.052	-0.003	-0.017***	-0.004***	-0.019***	-0.004**
<i>cxk</i>	0.035	-0.001	0.036	0.011**	0.002	-0.007***	0.003	-0.003***
<i>aocxa</i>	-0.047	0.037*	-0.05	0.035*	0.038	0.018***	0.054**	0.029***
<i>aocxl</i>	-0.149	0.013	-0.163	0.006	0.005	0.015**	0.017	0.015***
<i>aocxk</i>	0.059	-0.011	0.114	0.017	0.034**	0.033***	0.025**	0.017***
<i>aooxa</i>	-0.014	0.000	-0.01	0.001	-0.006*	-0.001	-0.004	0.001
<i>aooxl</i>	0.003	-0.004	0.001	-0.005	-0.003	-0.011***	-0.003	-0.01***
<i>aooxk</i>	0.007	-0.003	0.004	0.002	0.002	0.002***	0.002	0.001
<i>art</i>	0.006	0.001	0.019	0.000	-0.001	-0.003***	-0.001	-0.005***
<i>lxt</i>	0.000	-0.003	-0.005	-0.002	0.002	0.006***	0.001	0.006***
<i>kxt</i>	0.021***	-0.008***	0.022***	-0.007***	-0.005***	-0.006***	-0.003**	-0.002***
<i>cxt</i>	-0.005	0.001	-0.006	0.000	0.000	-0.001***	0.000	-0.001***
<i>aocxt</i>	-0.004	0.005***	-0.012	0.004***	0.004*	0.002***	0.004**	0.002***
<i>aooxt</i>	-0.002**	0.001	-0.002*	0.001**	-0.001**	0.000	-0.001***	0.000**
<i>meana</i>	-0.032	-0.011	-0.052	-0.074	0.049	-0.011	-0.001	-0.052***
<i>meanl</i>	-0.232*	-0.139***	-0.241*	-0.161***	-0.144***	-0.175***	-0.165***	-0.21***
<i>meank</i>	-0.153*	-0.054**	-0.108	0.011	-0.111***	-0.074***	-0.057***	-0.018***

Notes: Spec. 1 = Contract work in Capital. Spec. 2 = Contract work in Material.

Table A16: Comparison of Results between CZ and DE in Meat IDF

Type <i>Est.</i>	Organic				Conventional			
	Spec. 1		Spec. 2		Spec. 1		Spec. 2	
	CZ	DE	CZ	DE	CZ	DE	CZ	DE
<i>const.</i>	-0.207***	-0.153***	-0.192***	-0.14***	0.000***	N/A	-0.193***	N/A
<i>a</i>	-0.225***	-0.226***	-0.231***	-0.258***	0.000***	N/A	-0.278***	N/A
<i>l</i>	-0.103***	-0.104*	-0.095***	-0.128**	0.012***	N/A	-0.195**	N/A
<i>k</i>	-0.027*	0.019	-0.033**	-0.018	0.362***	N/A	-0.035	N/A
<i>t</i>	0.000	-0.006**	0.003**	-0.002	0.483***	N/A	0.000	N/A
<i>c</i>	-0.098***	-0.126***	-0.09***	-0.147***	0.000***	N/A	-0.108***	N/A
<i>aoc</i>	-0.202***	-0.052***	-0.205***	-0.05***	0.000***	N/A	-0.208***	N/A
<i>aoo</i>	-0.005***	-0.025***	-0.004***	-0.027***	0.022***	N/A	-0.008***	N/A
<i>aa</i>	-0.015	0.081	-0.044	-0.038	0.861**	N/A	0.104	N/A
<i>ll</i>	0.037	0.121	0.018	0.053	0.038***	N/A	-0.224*	N/A
<i>kk</i>	-0.002	-0.011	0.007	-0.019	0.53**	N/A	-0.03**	N/A
<i>tt</i>	0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	0.231***	N/A	0.001	N/A
<i>cc</i>	-0.017***	-0.007	-0.017***	-0.011***	0.000***	N/A	-0.033***	N/A
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.084***	-0.01***	-0.095***	-0.01***	0.008***	N/A	-0.064**	N/A
<i>aooaoo</i>	-0.002**	-0.003*	-0.001	-0.004**	0.301***	N/A	-0.001	N/A
<i>aw</i>	-0.029	-0.056	0.016	0.017	0.348*	N/A	0.009	N/A
<i>ak</i>	0.008	0.102***	0.004	0.093***	0.359***	N/A	-0.034	N/A
<i>lk</i>	-0.003	-0.083*	-0.043*	-0.039	0.617***	N/A	0.008	N/A
<i>chaoc</i>	0.002	0.01**	0.001	0.008**	0.699***	N/A	0.007	N/A
<i>chaoo</i>	0.002	0.006	0.002	0.016***	0.237***	N/A	0.003**	N/A
<i>aocxaoo</i>	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002**	0.962***	N/A	0.000	N/A
<i>cha</i>	0.009	-0.049**	0.008	-0.045*	0.747***	N/A	-0.013	N/A
<i>cxl</i>	-0.002	-0.013	0.004	0.009	0.089*	N/A	0.058*	N/A
<i>cxk</i>	-0.001	0.043*	0.002	0.014	0.3**	N/A	0.044***	N/A
<i>aocxa</i>	0.05***	0.004	0.04**	0.002	0.634**	N/A	0.007	N/A
<i>aocxl</i>	0.019	-0.006	0.023	-0.004	0.202*	N/A	0.083*	N/A
<i>aocxk</i>	0.012	-0.007	0.034***	-0.003	0.867***	N/A	-0.006	N/A
<i>aooxa</i>	-0.008***	-0.008	-0.008***	-0.024***	0.828***	N/A	-0.001	N/A
<i>aooxl</i>	0.005	-0.016	0.003	-0.011	0.113***	N/A	-0.011*	N/A
<i>aooxk</i>	0.002	-0.005	0.003*	-0.002	0.284***	N/A	0.003	N/A
<i>axt</i>	0.012***	0.018***	0.013***	0.013**	0.045***	N/A	-0.017***	N/A
<i>lxt</i>	-0.005	-0.001	-0.006	0.000	0.057***	N/A	-0.012*	N/A
<i>kxt</i>	-0.004*	-0.003	-0.005***	-0.001	0.849***	N/A	0.006*	N/A
<i>cxt</i>	0.001	-0.004	0.000	-0.004	0.933***	N/A	-0.001	N/A
<i>aocxt</i>	0.002	-0.001	0.002	-0.001	0.000**	N/A	0.015***	N/A
<i>aooxt</i>	-0.001**	-0.002	-0.001**	-0.001	0.571***	N/A	0.000	N/A
<i>meana</i>	-0.095**	0.065	-0.142***	-0.025	0.301***	N/A	-0.082	N/A
<i>meanl</i>	-0.092**	-0.15**	-0.087**	-0.093	0.669***	N/A	-0.047	N/A
<i>meank</i>	-0.02	-0.232***	0.012	-0.082**	0.81**	N/A	0.009	N/A

Table A17: Results of First step NLSUR Cereals Estimation for Precision farming

	Fertilisers Cost Share Equation		Pesticides Cost Share Equation
<i>const.</i>	0.02***	<i>const.</i>	0.047***
<i>f</i>	0.005***	<i>p</i>	0.005***
<i>p</i>	0.000	<i>f</i>	-0.006***
<i>a</i>	-0.005***	<i>a</i>	-0.001***
<i>l</i>	0.001	<i>l</i>	0.002***
<i>k</i>	0.001**	<i>k</i>	0.001***
<i>t</i>	0.000	<i>t</i>	0.000***
<i>m</i>	0.000	<i>m</i>	0.000*
<i>aoc</i>	-0.002	<i>aoc</i>	-0.001***
<i>aoo</i>	0.000**	<i>aoo</i>	0.000***
<i>d_f</i>	0.003	<i>d_p</i>	0.000***

Table A18: Precision Farming Model

Variable	Estimate and p-value	Variable	Estimate and p-value
<i>const.</i>	-0.072***	<i>cxk</i>	0.041**
<i>a</i>	-0.185**	<i>aocxa</i>	-0.092**
<i>l</i>	-0.076	<i>aocxl</i>	0.004
<i>k</i>	-0.074**	<i>aocxk</i>	0.02
<i>t</i>	0.073	<i>aooxa</i>	-0.009*
<i>c</i>	-0.088***	<i>aooxl</i>	0.006
<i>aoc</i>	-0.163***	<i>aooxk</i>	0.005**
<i>aoo</i>	-0.022***	<i>axt</i>	0.044
<i>aa</i>	0.18	<i>lxt</i>	-0.041
<i>ll</i>	0.013	<i>kxt</i>	-0.072*
<i>kk</i>	-0.041***	<i>cxt</i>	-0.003
<i>tt</i>	-0.026	<i>aocxt</i>	0.029*
<i>cc</i>	0.013	<i>aooxt</i>	0.001
<i>aocaoc</i>	-0.028***	<i>meana</i>	-0.182***
<i>aooaoo</i>	-0.006***	<i>meanl</i>	-0.242***
<i>aw</i>	0.139**	<i>meank</i>	0.002
<i>ak</i>	0.06	<i>Prec_{da}</i>	0.25*
<i>lk</i>	-0.134***	<i>Prec_{dl}</i>	0.114
<i>cxaooc</i>	0.065***	<i>Prec_{dk}</i>	0.035
<i>cxaooc</i>	0.000	<i>Prec_{dc}</i>	-0.182*
<i>aocxaoo</i>	0.000	<i>Prec_{daoc}</i>	-0.169***
<i>cxaa</i>	-0.13**	<i>Prec_{daoo}</i>	0.000
<i>cxl</i>	-0.015	<i>Prec_{dt}</i>	0.024

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